

E³UDRES²
**ent.r.e.
novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

Deliverable D4.3 | ENTRN DEL 4.3.01/2025

OS/OI/OE strategy and implementation plan for the
consortium | Date 06-May-2025

This page intentionally left blank.

Document Summary

Deliverable Title: OS/OI/OE strategy and implementation plan for the consortium
Deliverable number: D4.3
Type: Report
Version: 1.0
ID code: ENTRN DEL 4.3.01/2025
Deliverable Lead: UPT
Related Work package: WP4
Author(s): Diana Andone, Vlad Mihaescu, Muguras Mocofan (UPT), Ann Reulens (UCLL), Catarina Paz, Marta Frade (IPS), Stefan Kilian, Tassilo Pelegrini (STPUAS), István Temesi, Arnold Csonka, Klaudia Polgár (MATE), Agnese Dāvidsone, Evita Lantrāte (ViA)
Communication level: Public
Grant Agreement Number: 101071317
Project name: E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators: Cooperating for excellence and impact in research and innovation
Acronym: E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators
Start date of Project: 01-10-2022
Project coordinator: Luís Coelho (IPS)
Duration: 36 months
Deliverable Date: 06-05-2025
Reviewed by: Susanne Roiser (STPUAS) Date of review: 05-05-2025
Approved by: Luís Coelho (IPS) Approval date: 06-05-2025

Abstract

This report presents the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators OS/OI/OE strategy and implementation plan for the consortium**, developed in the WP4 during the last period and taking into account the work done in the project, consultation with other WPs.

Table of contents

Abstract	4
Table of contents	5
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	6
Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms	7
Executive Summary	9
1 E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators OS/OI/OE/OA Strategy Vision and Principles	10
1.1 Vision	10
1.2 Methodology	10
1.3 Theoretical background for Building innovation ecosystems: Insights from connectivism and Networks of Practice	11
2 The architecture of the open ecosystem for E³UDRES² R&I within the views of Open practices	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 The 4 key roles in every node	15
3 Governance and ethical structures for the Node on Open Practices from the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS)	17
3.1. Node Principles and Vision	17
3.1.1 Mission	18
3.2 Establishing the Open Practices Committee	19
3.3 Node for Open Practices – Governance, Policies and Strategies, Ethical considerations	20
3.3.1 Ethical considerations	22
4 Structures for collaboration, raising awareness and training, funding incentives for the Node on Open Practices from the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS) 24	
4.1 Training Initiatives	24
4.2 Raising Awareness	24
4.3 Collaboration	25
4.4 Funding incentives	26
4.5 EU Level Funding for OE/OA/OS/OI	26
5 Implementation plan for open practices and citizen science: Actions for the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS)	28
5.1 The four roles for Node Open practices & Citizen Science	28
5.2 Implementation Plan for Node Open Practices and Citizen Science	32
6 References	40
ANNEX I Open practices Strategies and Implementation plans at the level of each university in the Consortium	41

A.1.1 – Governance and Mission in the Node Open practices for each partner university	41
A.1.2 – Policies	43
A.1.3 – Training, Support and Infrastructures.....	46
A.1.4 – Collaboration and partnerships.....	48
A.1.5 – Monitoring and evaluation	49
A.1.6 – Funding and incentives.....	50
A.1.7 – EU Funding and incentives.....	51
ANNEX II Roles & responsibilities for each action of the Implementation Plan for Node OP&CS	56
ANNEX III Comprehensive KPI Monitoring for Node Open Practices & Citizen Science Implementation Plan	63

List of Figures

Figure 1 – E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem: Multi-Level Structure	15
--	----

List of Tables

Table 1 – Overview of each role within the ecosystem.....	16
---	----

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic University of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

AMGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement

DoA – Description of Action

DMP – Data Management Plan

E³UDRES² – Engaged European Entrepreneurial University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

EB – Executive Board

EEAB – External Expert Advisory Board

EU – European Union

FO – Financial Officer

GA – Grant Agreement

GnA – General Assembly

HR – Human Resources

HRS4R – Human Resources Strategi for Research

IT – Information Technology

KoM – Kick-off Meeting

OA – Open Access

OE – Open Education

OER – Open Education Resources

OI – Open Innovation

ORE – Open Research Europe

OS – Open Science

PC – Project Coordinator

Project No 101071317

PM – Person-Month

PO – Project Officer

REA – European Research Executive Agency

RI – Research Infrastructures

RP – Reporting Period

SEDIA – Single Electronic Data Interchange Area (Funding & tender opportunities)

SWOT – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

This report represents the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators OS/OI/OE strategy and implementation plan for the consortium**, developed in the WP4 during the last period and taking into account the work done in the project and consultation with other WPs. The Vision for the Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Open Access (OS/OI/OE/OA) and citizen science is to foster a culture of openness, collaboration, and accessibility in research and education, enhancing knowledge sharing, empowering communities and researchers alike to contribute to shared societal progress. As to accomplish this vision and mission of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project some key policies and governance aspects are envisioned:

- Establish an Open Practices Committee for strategy development at E³UDRES²
- Develop E³UDRES² policies on OE/OA/OS/OI based on the model of R&I ecosystem
- Enhance the acceptance and engagement for OE/OA/OS/OI at the E³UDRES² level

The E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem uses an innovative strategic model that redefines regional innovation, grounded in principles of openness, co-creation, and democratic governance. The dynamic model includes four key roles: Pillars (strategic leadership), Nexus (core of innovation), Sparks (emerging initiatives and collaborations), and Waves (impact and dissemination). These roles operate within Nodes or Networks of Practice, which focus on thematic areas like Shared R&I, Open Practices, Citizen Science, and Human Resources. It includes a synthesis of the E³UDRES² research and innovation ecosystem model, incorporating *open governance, roles policies, ethics, access, training, support and infrastructures, different models of funding and incentives, for collaboration and partnerships, including monitoring and evaluation and an implementation plan*, for OS/OI/OE/OA and citizen science in the Ent-r-e-novators higher education institutions.

1 E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators OS/OI/OE/OA Strategy Vision and Principles

1.1 Vision

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Vision for the Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Open Access (OS/OI/OE/OA) and Citizen Science is to foster a culture of openness, collaboration, and accessibility in research and education, enhancing knowledge sharing, empowering communities and researchers alike to contribute to shared societal progress.

As to accomplish this vision and mission of the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project** some key policies and governance aspects are envisioned:

- Establish an **Open Practices Committee** for strategy development at **E³UDRES²**
- Develop E³UDRES² policies on OE/OA/OS/OI based on the model of R&I ecosystem
- Enhance the acceptance and engagement for OE/OA/OS/OI at the **E³UDRES²** level

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project places Open Science (OS), Open Innovation (OI), Open Education (OE), and Open Access (OA) at the heart of its strategy to transform small and medium-sized European regions into smart and sustainable innovation ecosystems. These four pillars are integral to the project's mission of fostering collaborative, inclusive, and forward-thinking research and education practices.

1.2 Methodology

In the **E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project**, based on the previous documents developed during the project and the result from **D4.1 Report on the Identified Practices, Barriers and Needs for Strengthening Open Research, Open Science and Technology Transfer Between Partners** and the **D4.2 Report on the SWOT analysis of training offers/needs in OS/OI/OE/OA and Development of a training curricula for providing OS/OI/OE/OA skills and competences**, and the following activities performed we have approached the development of the E³UDRES² OS/OI/OE/OA Strategy with a new methodology.

We investigated different strategic developments and envisioned a strategic eco-system that will allow co-creation and openness at the core of its vision. A synthesis of the E³UDRES² research and innovation ecosystem model, incorporating *open governance, roles policies, ethics, access, training, support and infrastructures, different models of funding and incentives, for collaboration and partnerships, including monitoring and evaluation and an implementation plan*, for **Open**

Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Open Access (OS/OI/OE/OA) and Citizen Science in the Ent-r-e-novators higher education institutions.

The E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem will use an innovative strategic model that redefines regional innovation. Grounded in principles of openness, co-creation, and democratic governance, the ecosystem model connects universities, industry, governments, and society.

This model closes a critical gap: the need for agile, flexible, and regionally rooted ecosystems that can adapt to changing policy landscapes, fragmented institutional goals, and limited collaboration infrastructures. The vision promotes a 'just co-existence' where diverse actors co-create knowledge to address global and local challenges. This model is based on principles of organic growth, open knowledge, infrastructure sharing, and democratic decision-making. The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem functions as a living network where different partners work together to drive innovation and societal impact.

The model we propose looks into the research and innovation aspect as a whole and foresees open practices and citizen science as an integrate part of it. For this reason, several aspects of the proposed eco-system model are a result of joint discussions with the other WPs from this project.

The strategic open ecosystem model is built on a dynamic model that includes four key roles: **Pillars** (strategic leadership), **Nexus** (core of innovation), **Sparks** (emerging initiatives and collaborations), and **Waves** (impact and dissemination). These roles operate within **Nodes** or Networks of Practice, which focus on thematic areas like Shared R&I, Open Practices, Citizen Science, and Human Resources, aligned with the key focus areas of the Ent-r-e-novators project. An overarching **R&I Steering Board** for the whole R&I provides governance, ensures strategic direction, and aligns the ecosystem's goals with broader policies and institutional priorities. This **R&I Steering Board** will be including the **Open Practices Committee which will have main responsibilities over the Node of Open Practices and Citizen Science**.

This collaborative model fosters innovation, adaptability, and sustainable growth.

1.3 Theoretical background for Building innovation ecosystems: Insights from connectivism and Networks of Practice

The conceptual foundation of the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem is built upon a rich theoretical framework rooted in contemporary understandings of knowledge sharing, learning, innovation, and collaboration. It synthesizes insights from *Connectivism*, *Networks of Practice*, *Communities of Practice*, and the broader study of the *social life of information*, to shape a model capable of responding to the complex challenges of modern regional and global innovation landscapes. These

concepts are seen also within the experience on applying them for digital transformation strategies for universities.

Connectivism, introduced by George Siemens (2005) and further elaborated by Jon Dron and Terry Anderson (2014), redefines learning in the digital age as the ability to build, navigate, and maintain meaningful networks of information and expertise. In this view, knowledge is not contained within individuals but exists across distributed networks, and learning involves identifying and making connections across diverse fields, ideas, and communities. This paradigm shift, foundational to the development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Open Educational resources (OERs) and digital learning environments, have been used by one of the partners, Politehnica University of Timisoara, in their development of the digital strategy, mainly the digital education strategy (UPT, EDEN, 2020). Based on this experience and further enhanced by the validation of the EUA Digital Transformation Map for the higher education (2024) and the EUA Strategy and Organizational Culture Report (2022), we have looked into the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem's emphasis on open knowledge sharing, interdisciplinary collaboration, and dynamic network-building across regions and sectors.

The concept of **Networks of Practices (NoPs)**, as articulated by Wasko and Faraj (2005) and summarized in subsequent academic discussions (Lesser & Storck, 2013), emphasizes how geographically dispersed individuals sharing a common professional practice can form loosely connected networks for exchanging knowledge and expertise. NoPs are crucial mechanisms for integrating fragmented knowledge and promoting collective learning across boundaries. An idea that is central to the creation of thematic Nodes within the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem, where diverse stakeholders collaboratively engage in problem-solving and innovation.

Furthermore, the ecosystem's model draws heavily on Communities of Practice (CoP) theory (Wenger, 1998; Wenger, McDermott, & Snyder, 2002), which posits that learning is fundamentally a social process. CoPs form around shared domains of interest, where members engage in collective activities, share information, and evolve their practices over time. This principle underlines the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem's commitment to fostering long-term, self-sustaining communities that continuously generate and apply knowledge to address societal challenges.

Additionally, the seminal work of John Seely Brown and Paul Duguid (2000) on the *social life of information* provides a broader epistemological context, highlighting how information gains meaning through human interpretation and social engagement. Their insights reinforce the ecosystem's focus on promoting open, meaningful interactions among different actors, ensuring that knowledge does not remain abstract but becomes actionable within social and regional contexts.

Together, these theoretical influences underpin the **E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem's approach**:

- prioritizing flexibility and adaptability over rigid structures,
- fostering cross-sectoral collaboration and democratic governance,
- encouraging co-creation and shared ownership of knowledge and innovation,
- and maintaining strong regional roots while remaining globally interconnected.

By grounding itself in these interconnected theories, the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem aspires to function not merely as a project or network, but as a living, evolving system capable of continuously responding to emerging societal and technological needs.

This strategic model is not just a random structure, it is grounded in powerful theories (Connectivism, Networks of Practice (NoPs), Communities of Practice (CoPs) and Social Life of Information) that have been tested in education, innovation, and knowledge management. In the E³UDRES² Alliance one partner, UPT, have been working with them for more than a decade, as they are at the core development of their digital transformation. Another partner, UCLL, have used some principles from these theories in their business innovation development.

It shows that the E³UDRES² consortium is building the E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem in a way that matches how knowledge and innovation really happen today: flexible, networked, regionally rooted but globally aware and focused on social learning and co-creation. It positions the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem as a forward-looking alliance that understands how innovation and knowledge truly emerge in the modern world.

2 The architecture of the open ecosystem for E³UDRES² R&I within the views of Open practices

2.1 Introduction

We introduce here the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem, which is going to be a core part of the WP2 and **D2.4 E³UDRES² common R&I agenda and action plan**, as well as the **D3.6 Strategy & implementation plan for efficient, sustainable and agile RD&I sharing network** and it is briefly explained here for clarity.

The **E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem** operates as an integrated, multi-layered system built on four interdependent roles: **Pillars, Nexus, Sparks, and Waves**, see Figure 1. These are the roles that different people of the partner institutions will take on within the ecosystem. These roles are undertaken by individuals from partner institutions, each with distinct responsibilities, relationships, and contributions. Each role is actively performed by real actors, and while they are distinct, they are interconnected in advancing the ecosystem's strategic goals, enhancing innovation capacity, and driving societal impact.

Each role in the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem is essential and functions synergistically:

- Pillars provide strategic foresight and values.
- Nexus ensures co-creation and governance.
- Sparks deliver experimentation and project energy.
- Waves achieve scaling, dissemination, societal change and impact.

Nodes – Networks of Practices

Individuals will assume these roles within Networks of Practices (NoPs), we will refer to them as 'nodes'. These NoPs, or nodes, are thematically organized, serving as collaborative hubs where expertise and knowledge converge around specific areas of focus. Each node operates as a dynamic, interdisciplinary space, facilitating the exchange of ideas, fostering innovation, and advancing the ecosystem's strategic objectives. The thematic focus of each node enhances the overall coherence and efficacy of the ecosystem, driving forward both its intellectual and societal impact through specialized contributions from its members.

E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem: Multi-Level Structure

Figure 1 – E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem: Multi-Level Structure

The initial themes of the nodes align with the core topics of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project: Open Practices and Citizen Science, and Shared R&I and HR. These themes are integral to the R&I ecosystem, as they address essential aspects of collaboration, innovation, and human resources that are vital for the ecosystem's long-term sustainability. By embedding these topics into the strategy, the ecosystem ensures that it remains both future-proof and agile. The focus on Open Practices and Citizen Science, alongside Shared R&I and HR, fosters a flexible, inclusive environment that encourages innovation, enhances interdisciplinary collaboration, and strengthens the ecosystem's overall resilience, enabling it to adapt to emerging challenges and opportunities. Moreover, the integration of these themes is not just a strategic choice but a commitment to implement and anchor lessons learned and best practices within the alliance. This continuous process of reflection and adaptation is key to evolving the ecosystem. To achieve this, we aim to actively monitor progress, assess outcomes, and, importantly, continuously improve our approaches, ensuring that the ecosystem remains dynamic, responsive, and capable of achieving its long-term goals.

2.2 The 4 key roles in every node

The E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem is designed to facilitate both **vertical** and **horizontal** collaboration, ensuring that all parts of the system work together seamlessly to achieve the ecosystem's goals. The ecosystem is structured into four interdependent roles, each focusing on a specific area of impact and ensuring the system's overall functionality and success. These roles are designed to be dynamic and complementary, with each group collaborating across different levels of the ecosystem. While each role is responsible for its core responsibilities, they work in close

coordination to drive continuous innovation, foster cross-sector collaboration, and ensure that the ecosystem remains responsive to both local and global challenges.

In Table 1 is presented a short overview of each role within the ecosystem.

Table 1 – Overview of each role within the ecosystem

Role	Area of impact
Pillars	Provide strategic foresight and long-term thematic vision (Policy, EU policy alignment, ...)
Nexus	Serves as the collaborative center for dialogue, co-creation, and sociocratic decision-making. <i>Cross nexus sessions: to share output created in each node</i>
Sparks	Experimental units where interdisciplinary teams launch pilot projects.
Waves	Ensure dissemination, scaling, and systemic impact.
Core	Overarching Steering Board (accountables)

This structure enables flexible and coordinated collaboration at all levels of the ecosystem, ensuring each role contributes to the overall impact while staying focused on its specific purpose.

3 Governance and ethical structures for the Node on Open Practices from the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS)

Based on the strategy of the ecosystem model.

This Node will be guided by the following definitions which we have outlined in (D4.1):

- **Open Education (OE):** Open education encompasses resources, tools and practices that employ a framework of open sharing.
- **Open Science (OS):** The practice of making scientific research, data, and dissemination accessible to everyone.
- **Open Access (OA):** The free and unrestricted access to scientific information and research findings.
- **Open Innovation (OI):** A model that encourages collaboration between institutions, industries, and communities to foster creative solutions.
- **Citizen Science (CS):** Involving citizens in the whole scientific process, allowing them to collect data, participate in research, and contribute to scientific discovery.

3.1. Node Principles and Vision

The guiding principles for the Open Practices and Citizen Science Node are:

- **Accessibility:** Ensuring that knowledge is openly accessible to all.
- **Transparency:** Promoting open methodologies, peer review, and data sharing.
- **Collaboration:** Encouraging interdisciplinary and global cooperation.
- **Equity & Inclusion:** Supporting diverse participation, multilingual resources, and broad accessibility.
- **Sustainability:** Ensuring long-term open access, repository maintenance, and continuous capacity building.

And precisely for **E³UDRES²**:

- **Promote transparent and reproducible research through Open Access and Open Science practices.**
- **Improve access to education with Open Education initiatives.**
- **Encourage innovation, inclusivity, and participation through Open Innovation and citizen science.**

Open education, open science, and open innovation are transformative movements aimed at enhancing accessibility, transparency, and collaboration in education, research, and innovation. These movements are supported by specific governance structures and policies that facilitate their implementation and growth.

This response explores the key governance structures and policies that underpin these open practices based on our findings from the:

- [1] D4.1 Report on identified practices – identifies opportunities for collaboration and policy development to address challenges and capitalize on open science initiatives barriers needs
- [2] D4.2 ENTRENOVATORS SWOT training in OS_OI_OE_OA

Based on the results from these reports we identified the governance and mission specifics for E³UDRES².

Promoting Openness and Accessibility

- The alliance envisions a future where educational resources, scientific research, and innovative practices are openly accessible to all, removing barriers to knowledge and fostering a culture of inclusivity [1] [2].
- By integrating open practices into institutional policies and strategies, the alliance aims to enhance the visibility and impact of research and innovation on a global scale [1].

Fostering Collaboration and Innovation

- The vision includes creating a collaborative network of institutions and stakeholders that work together to co-create and innovate, leveraging shared resources and expertise [1].
- The alliance seeks to establish platforms and hubs that facilitate international collaboration and multidisciplinary interactions, thereby accelerating innovation and aligning education with market needs [1].

3.1.1 Mission

Developing Strategic Frameworks

- The mission involves formulating clear policies and strategic plans for open education, open science, open access, and open innovation, guiding institutions in their efforts to embrace open practices [1].
- The alliance aims to support the development of joint curricula and training programs that equip learners with the skills and competencies necessary to engage in open research and innovation [1].

Empowering Stakeholders

- A key mission objective is to empower students, researchers, and educators by providing them with the tools and mindset required to participate in open knowledge sharing and innovation [1].
- The alliance is committed to fostering a culture of transparency and collaboration in academia, preparing the next generation of professionals to navigate the evolving landscape of open practices [1].

Enhancing Institutional Reputation and Funding Opportunities

- By adopting a unified approach to open practices, the alliance seeks to enhance the reputation of participating institutions and create more funding opportunities from global organizations and private partnerships [1].
- The mission includes advocating for policy improvements and government partnerships to support open innovation initiatives and overcome regulatory barriers [1].

3.2 Establishing the Open Practices Committee

The main aim of the **Open Practices Committee** in the E³UDRES² Alliance is to develop, implement, and continually refine a cohesive strategy that promotes and embeds open access, open science, open education and open innovation practices across the Alliance and transfer the knowledge and experience to all member institutions. The Committee is the overarching body (**Pillar and Core**) for the **Node on Open Practices**, part of the **R&I Steering Board** and with **main responsibilities over the Node of Open Practices and Citizen Science**.

Roles

Understand the roles in the Node, overseeing the Nexus and identify the Sparks and ensure the continued functionalities in the Waves. It is part of the Core, with an overarching views and responsibilities.

Policy development for the open practices within the pillars foresight - Lead the formulation, review and updating of open practice policies and guidelines that align with E³UDRES² Alliance goals.

Identifying the sparks, raising awareness, engagement and communication – Act as the primary liaison between member institutions, faculty, researchers, and external partners, ensuring transparent communication and inclusive participation in open practice initiatives.

Capacity building, best practices, resource coordination – organize workshops and seminars, summer schools, courses and training, continuously identify training needs, and coordinate resources to adopt and implement open practices effectively and this strategy.

Monitoring and Impact - Establish mechanisms to track progress, evaluating the impact of open initiatives, and reporting findings to guide continuous improvement and strategic adjustments.

The roles will be supported and integrated in an iterative mechanism; part of the democratic decision-making identified in this strategy. The Committee as a pillar will facilitate a sociocratic voting mechanism to determine the strategic direction and priority projects within the ecosystem, when needed: the policies, communication, engagement, capacity building and resource coordination will be continually evaluated on a yearly basis to allow for transparency and accountability.

3.3 Node for Open Practices – Governance, Policies and Strategies, Ethical considerations

For each of the open practices we identified in the previous work, in the SOWT and PEST analysis and in the activities carried in this year the main characteristics and structures for Governance, Policies and Strategies, as well as the Ethical considerations, which we will continue to integrate in the node for Open Practices.

Open Education (OE)

Governance Structures

- Institutional Commitment: Some universities actively participate in open education initiatives, with institutions like UPT and MATE leading by example through workshops and events dedicated to open education [2].
- Diverse Commitment Levels: The partnership shows diversity in its commitment to open education, with varying levels of engagement and support for open education practices [2].

Policies and Strategies

- Policy Development: There is an opportunity for the consortium to develop comprehensive open education policies, which can enhance collaboration and resource sharing among institutions [2].
- Strategic Priorities: The importance assigned to open education varies across universities, which can lead to inconsistencies in policy implementation [2].
- Support Lifelong Learning: Providing flexible learning pathways through initiatives like micro-credentials and joint degrees. The strategy will be addressed by joint learning provisions and digitalisation infrastructure and deepening collaboration through strong digital foundations, supporting open and flexible learning environments.

Open Science (OS)

Governance Structures

- Institutional Policies: Most institutions have an open science policy and strategy, ensuring commitment and support for open science practices [2].
- International Collaborations: Open science benefits from political endorsements and international collaborations, which are crucial for its implementation [2].

Policies and Strategies

- FAIR Principles: Some institutions prioritize the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) as part of their strategic targets, which guide data management and sharing practices [2].
- Open Access Publishing: Institutions support open access publishing through internal funding mechanisms and the use of open-source software [2].

Open access (OA)

Governance Structures

- Institutional Policies and Guidelines: Most institutions promote open access.
- Some universities have established open access policies that serve as a foundation for institutions that have yet to develop such frameworks [2].
- Institutional guidelines often include the use of digital repositories for storing publications, which supports the broader goals of open access.

Policies and Strategies

- Strategic Importance and Implementation: commit to the FAIR principles.
- Many universities are still in the planning stages of establishing comprehensive open access strategies, indicating a need for more effective adoption of open access principles [1].

Open Innovation (OI)

Governance Structures

- Strategic Priority: Open innovation is a strategic priority for many institutions, although awareness and involvement among staff are limited [1] [2].
- Collaboration Networks: Institutions have networks of staff and external stakeholders to support open innovation, although these are often limited [2].

Policies and Strategies

- Policy and Strategy Development: Some institutions have developed open innovation policies or strategies, but there is a need for more comprehensive approaches across the consortium [2].

- Co-Creation Labs: The establishment of co-creation labs and makerspaces is encouraged to enhance multidisciplinary collaboration and innovation [2].

Open practices are recognized as important within university policies, but there is often a gap between its perceived importance and actual implementation.

3.3.1 Ethical considerations

- Open access promotes transparency by providing free access to scientific information, but it raises concerns about the standards and integrity of peer review processes [2].
- There is a need to navigate and overcome legal and regulatory barriers, such as copyright issues, to support open access implementation [2].
- Open science emphasizes transparency and reproducibility, but it requires careful consideration of open methodologies and peer review processes to maintain research integrity [2].
- Adopting a data steward and open data policy at the level of the Alliance, with integration of data stewards of the HEIs and their responsibility for ensuring the quality, integrity, accessibility and proper governance of data within our organizations and refer to their key responsibilities such as data quality management, metadata management, data governance and compliance, data access and sharing, support for OS, with training & advocacy.
- The language barrier, where most open educational resources (OERs) are in English, can limit accessibility for non-English-speaking students [2].
- The use of free and creative common licenses is essential for open education, but a lack of awareness about how to use these licenses appropriately can hinder their incorporation into curricula [2].
- Quality and Sustainability: Concerns about the quality and effectiveness of open educational resources can arise if they are poorly developed [2].
- The sustainability of open education initiatives may be threatened by economic challenges, including limited internal budgets [2].
- Open innovation involves engaging with external partners, which necessitates upholding ethical standards and integrity in collaborative practices [2].
- There is a need for clear policies and guidelines to manage intellectual property and prevent data leakage during open innovation projects [2].

Data Sharing and Privacy

- The willingness to navigate legal barriers, such as GDPR regulations, is crucial for the responsible sharing of research data in open science [2].
- Technological threats, such as data breaches, pose significant risks to open access, necessitating strong policies to protect sensitive information [2].

Legal and Regulatory Considerations

- Legal and regulatory barriers, such as shifts in copyright regulation, pose threats to the swift implementation of open access [2].
- Institutions must navigate these challenges to ensure compliance and support for open access initiatives [1].

In conclusion, the alliance's vision and mission are centered on creating an open and collaborative environment that drives innovation and knowledge sharing. While there are existing frameworks and strategies, there is a need for more comprehensive and unified approaches to enhance collaboration and resource sharing, still guaranteeing a misuse of open data or innovation of openly shared information. Future directions may involve expanding the network of participating institutions and exploring new avenues for collaboration and innovation.

The Mission, Governance and Ethical considerations in the Node Open practices, for each partner university are in Annex 1.

4 Structures for collaboration, raising awareness and training, funding incentives for the Node on Open Practices from the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS)

In our previous work and SWOT analysis we identified that there is a significant need for training and awareness programs to improve communication and understanding of open practices within universities [1]. Recognized training programs for open access publications, open science and the use of open educational resources (OER) are already in place in some institutions, which can be leveraged to enhance open practices among the entire partnership [2].

4.1 Training Initiatives

A joint training program **Foundations for OE/OA/OS/OI** has been developed to provide comprehensive understanding and skills in open education, equipping learners to engage in open research and develop open educational resources [2]. This training is a transversal course and resources for an in-depth introduction to the principles, practices, and applications of OE/OA/OS/OI and is available online on a common structure, with access and information from the project E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators website.

The program includes also extra resources of over 100 courses and modules, some of which are already in use and are integrated as open educational resources (OERs) [2].

Training and education are crucial in addressing gaps in open access (OA) implementation, with librarians identified as key implementers.

We also have identified that there is a need for better adoption of principles like FAIR and unique researcher identifiers like ORCID, indicating areas for future training development and is also in first phase of implementation. We include also data sharing open data and training for the stewards of data management into our first phase implementation.

4.2 Raising Awareness

The partnership aims to increase awareness and foster a clearer vision for open practices by promoting the use of open resources and open licensing [2].

While there is growing support for OA publishing, communication and awareness within universities need improvement to bridge the gap between perceived importance and implementation.

The SWOT conducted highlights the mixed level of awareness and utilization of OP tools and resources across different universities, with some using different open structures for education (Moodle), for open publishing using DOI, and for open science in their institutional libraries (open access for the doctoral and master thesis, UPT own publishing house publishing open access some journals and books, etc.).

The importance of open science is recognized, but there is a significant gap between perceived importance and implementation, necessitating improved communication and awareness efforts, through events, webinars, workshops.

We have initiated a yearly **Open Practices International Workshop**, organised in hybrid mode, with open access publication and with widespread into the partnership. This is complemented by webinars and workshops, open days dedicated to open practices organised by each partner at their own institution.

4.3 Collaboration

The partnership shows diversity in commitment to open education, with some universities actively participating in initiatives and using OERs, although there are challenges such as lack of universal policies and limited evaluation. Some universities collaborate with external partners and associations (**Open Education Global, EDEN, COARA, European Open Science Cloud Association**) with dedicated activities towards open practices [2].

Collaboration opportunities are identified in policy development and securing financial support, despite potential resistance to change [2].

The structured interviews and surveys conducted across partner universities, and the partnership's SWOT analysis provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state of open policies and implementation strategies, facilitating informed decision-making and collaboration.

Future visions include increased inter-university cooperation in OA initiatives to enhance awareness and strategy implementation [1].

Some institutions have open innovation policies and measure success through KPIs, but this is limited to a few partners, indicating room for broader training initiatives [2].

The partnership supports open innovation through collaboration opportunities, policy formation, with Open innovation hubs, shared platforms, and co-creation labs are identified as facilitators of international collaboration and multidisciplinary interactions [2].

4.4 Funding incentives

Open education, open science, open access, and open innovation are initiatives that often require substantial funding and incentives to be effectively implemented and sustained. The following explore the opportunities for funding and incentives in each of these areas, drawing on insights from the previous SWOT and reports:

- Government policies that promote open education can provide funding or incentives for universities to embrace open educational practices
- Open education supports lifelong learning, allowing individuals to acquire new skills and knowledge, which can be incentivized through educational grants and scholarships
- Open science is embraced by research funders, universities, and the EU, indicating potential funding at the European level, such as through Horizon 2020
- Institutions actively supporting open access publishing, such as through their own journals or internal funding mechanisms, highlight opportunities for financial support aligned with open science principles. Some universities have internal funding available to publish open access papers, articles, and books, which supports the dissemination of research findings.
- The role of personal, institutional, and subject repositories in open access publishing suggests opportunities for funding to enhance these infrastructures. Public awareness and support for open science can influence the level of demand and acceptance of open access research, potentially leading to increased funding opportunities. The existence of institutional guidelines for open access and the availability of digital repositories serve as incentives for researchers to publish openly
- The establishment of OI hubs, shared platforms, and co-creation labs can facilitate international collaboration and attract funding
- The integration of open innovation into curricula and extracurricular activities can be incentivized through educational grants and industry partnerships

4.5 EU Level Funding for OE/OA/OS/OI

We mapped of some current EU funding strands that explicitly support open science, open education, and open innovation. Each entry gives the official programme (or specific call), a 1-sentence “why it matters,” typical beneficiaries, the budget/grant scale where available, and where to look for live or upcoming calls on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal or the programme’s own site.

Based on this mapping and within the support provided through this project, 1 application for the development and integration of open data have been applied, and others are envisioned.

This list is only indicative and not exhaustive and can be Found in Annex 1.

The collaboration, raising awareness and training, funding incentives considerations in the Node Open practices, for each partner university are in Annex 1.

5 Implementation plan for open practices and citizen science: Actions for the thematic Network of Practice (node OP&CS)

Based on the strategy of the ecosystem model.

The primary goal of the *node open practices and citizen science* is to carry out the actions, defined in the implementation plan, which are related to the node's key themes: Open Practices and Citizen Science. This plan outlines the collaborative efforts required to successfully integrate and implement open science practices (open science, open access, open innovation, open education, and citizen science) across the consortium's projects and initiatives. It serves as a roadmap to align all stakeholders on objectives, roles, processes, and timelines, ensuring a transparent, inclusive, and efficient approach to advancing open practices throughout the ecosystem.

5.1 The four roles for Node Open practices & Citizen Science

Leveraging the four roles for effective implementation and maintenance of open practices and citizen science throughout the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem.

To ensure the successful implementation and maintenance of open practices (op) and citizen science (cs) within our E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem, this thematic node will be taking proactive steps to implement, maintain, and enforce OP and CS across our consortium and partner institutions.

Within the node OP&CS the four defined roles — **Pillars**, **Nexus**, **Sparks**, and **Waves** — will be leveraged as the foundation for executing actions. These roles will not only support the development of the plan but will also be integral to the implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of progress.

In the following sections, we will outline the detailed implementation plan, describing how each role will contribute to executing and monitoring the actions. This plan will provide a clear overview of the actions, the roles involved, expected outcomes, and how progress will be monitored.

At the core of this implementation plan will stay the building of a fluid, living ecosystem that is self-governed, where the Open Practices Committee will play the key role of the pillar of the node, as only to set up direction, policies and assume a governance, but to share information and encourage the Nexus and the sparks to build up actions and activities.

For each action, we will define KPIs and regularly prepare progress reports to ensure that we remain on track. The roles will contribute as follows:

Pillars will set the strategic direction and vision, ensuring overall coordination of the plan. They are responsible for setting the overarching goals for open practices and citizen science within the ecosystem, ensuring alignment with national and European policies. They develop strategies to integrate and sustain open practices, while also ensuring equitable participation and access to training and resources. Additionally, the Pillars oversee the implementation of key performance indicators (KPIs) to track progress.

Strategically, the Pillars focus on strengthening open practices and citizen science to promote inclusivity, sustainability, and equitable knowledge sharing. They uphold shared values of openness, respect, interdisciplinary collaboration, and social responsibility. They will facilitate the democratic decision-making process within the node, with a voting mechanism to ensure that all perspectives are included when shaping priorities for open practices and citizen science. They will create the **Open Practices Committee** which will contain at least one person, for each of the open practices area, as the main contact and informing point in the university. They will be able to collaborate and facilitate the development and integration of open practices policies.

Nexus will act as the hub for knowledge-sharing and coordination between various stakeholders. The Nexus is the dynamic, beating heart of collaboration, innovation, and knowledge sharing. It serves as a vibrant hub where open practices and citizen science are seamlessly integrated into the ecosystem, driving forward education, research, and societal impact. By connecting educators, researchers, businesses, and communities, the Nexus sparks transformative ideas and fosters groundbreaking partnerships.

At the core of the Nexus' activities is its role in championing active collaboration, embedding citizen science in research and innovation, and co-creating cutting-edge digital tools that advance open practices and ethical research standards. The Nexus leads the way in shaping the future of open science through sociocratic decision-making, ensuring that all voices are heard in evaluating and selecting impactful projects. Moreover, it supports the development of new tools and methodologies, fostering innovation in controlled environments.

Strategically, the Nexus is dedicated to building a robust foundation for open practices and citizen science by fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration, embracing a shared vision, and empowering diverse stakeholders through democratic decision-making. By accelerating the adoption of open practices and citizen science, the Nexus is at the forefront of transformative change, driving the ecosystem toward a future of greater inclusivity, collaboration, and innovation.

Sparks will launch small-scale initiatives through pilot projects and case studies to gather practical insights. The Sparks are the relentless catalysts driving the generation of fresh ideas, breakthrough solutions, and transformative collaborations within open practices and citizen science. They are the heartbeat of innovation, fuelled by dynamic networks and working groups dedicated to addressing real-world challenges. These initiatives, both internal and external, bring together diverse minds and sectors, sparking creativity and forging impactful partnerships.

Key Sparks initiatives are at the forefront of collaborative research, with universities, industries, and governments joining forces to tackle complex societal issues. From policy labs focused on democratic policymaking to co-creating digital platforms that empower open-access publishing and knowledge sharing, the Sparks are laying the groundwork for a more inclusive and innovative future. Regional development efforts further fuel local ecosystems, driving innovation and strengthening connections between research and the communities it serves.

Strategically, the Sparks unite strategic networks of universities, businesses, and civil organizations, propelling collaborative and interdisciplinary projects that break down silos and foster cross-sectoral solutions. With a keen focus on thematic working groups, the Sparks accelerate the implementation of Open Practices and Citizen Science, ensuring that each initiative drives tangible societal change.

Waves will handle external communication of progress and results, enhancing the engagement of external stakeholders. The Waves represent the far-reaching ripple effects of the Nexus and Sparks' initiatives, creating waves of societal transformation that ripple through communities, industries, and policies. These outcomes go beyond immediate action; they drive lasting change that redefines the way we approach research, knowledge sharing, and community involvement in scientific processes.

Key outcomes of the Waves include open-access publications, participatory policy recommendations, and publicly available research tools that ensure inclusivity and transparency. These initiatives are not just about outputs — they're about empowering citizens to actively participate in the scientific process, scaling public engagement, and cultivating a culture of open research that shapes the future.

Strategically, the Waves focus on embedding open practices and citizen science into every layer of society. From capacity building, fostering digital literacy, and advocating for inclusive policies, to influencing policy and funding structures on regional and European levels, the Waves are the engine of broader change. Through open-access platforms, collaborative research, and meaningful citizen engagement, they ensure that research continues to address the most pressing challenges of our time, sparking real-world impact and societal transformation.

In the following sections, we will provide a detailed overview of each action outlined in the implementation plan of the node OP&CS, as well as the strategies for monitoring and evaluating their progress. This includes the specific Key Performance Indicators that will be used to track the effectiveness of the actions and ensure their successful execution.

5.2 Implementation Plan for Node Open Practices and Citizen Science

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
1. Establish the Open Practices Committee as a Network of Practitioners (Node) for Open Practices and Citizen Science at E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the strategic purpose and structure of the node. - Appoint 1 member from each partner university - Appoint key representatives from different sectors (education, research, industry, and government). - Align node objectives with EU policies and institutional priorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Act as the coordinating hub for open practices and citizen science knowledge creation - Organize meetings, workshops, and decision-making sessions. - Facilitate knowledge exchange between stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drive external collaboration by engaging stakeholders to expand the network - Pilot node activities through small working groups. - Develop preliminary recommendations for implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate and disseminate node progress to internal and external stakeholders. - Publish reports, guidelines, and policy recommendations. - Promote the node's role in cross-sector collaborations. - Amplify the impact of the network by scaling participation and fostering societal transformation. 	<p>Appoint full committee (100 % partner coverage + 4 external experts).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Hold kick-off retreat; create two pilot working groups (policy; training). ▶ Publish Year-1 work-plan & meeting calendar. 	<p>Partners represented ≥ 100 %</p> <p>≥ 4 formal meetings</p> <p>2 pilot-group reports produced</p>
2. Develop E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem Policies on OE/OA/OS/OI/CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set the policy framework and ensure alignment with European standards (e.g., FAIR data, Open EU education) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate discussions on best practices in policy development. - Engage university administrators, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design and develop prototype policy guidelines with external stakeholders and test their feasibility. - Conduct case studies on 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate finalized policies through open-access publications within each university Library and open access publications. 	<p>Identify open-data steward</p> <p>Hold 3 multi-stakeholder policy meetings</p> <p>Identify and integrate FAIR data</p>	<p>Stakeholders consulted ≥ 60</p> <p>Open-data steward appointed</p>

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	adoption, open practices.). - Define compliance guidelines for open access, research transparency, and citizen science. - Establish an open data steward and an open data management plan for the alliance	legal teams, and researchers in policy co-creation. - Ensure policies are adaptable for various institutional contexts. - Engage the innovators and ambassadors for OE/OA/OS/OI/CS from each university .	institutions successfully implementing OE/OA/OS/OI. - Pilot policy impact assessments.	- Organize policy advocacy events with external stakeholders. And integrate these in the workshops and webinars already established. - Collaborate with policymakers to scale policies beyond E³UDRES².	and Open education and Science policies	
3. Develop/ Integrate support and training for open practices and citizen science	- Integrate the MOOC course Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS , as the main training practices - Continue the Open Practices International Workshop , as a yearly event at international level, with open access published papers	- Integrate the MOOC course Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS as an interdisciplinary training programs for researchers, educators, policymakers, industry partners, and citizens. Validate the modules as microcredentials	- Ignite innovation: experiment with and promote new methods for open science and citizen science training. - Motivate to develop new modules and content for OE/OA/OS/OI/CS and integrate them at the Alliance level - Motivate participation to the	- Scale up successful programs across institutions: the Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS , the Open Practices PhD Summer school, workshops, webinars. - Organize webinars and public engagement initiatives to promote best	Launch MOOC (5 ECTS) on Arena as 5 microcredentials; open enrolments to other Alliances Deliver Open Practices International Workshop ≥ 5 local webinars, and 3 to new E³UDRES² partners 1 PhD Summer-School ▶ Spin up	MOOC live & ≥ 150 learners and microcertificates 2. Training events delivered ≥ 8 3. Knowledge-hub online

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue the development of local, integrated by each partner, workshops, webinars, open days for open practices - Allocate funding and resources for training initiatives. - Further develop the Open Practices PhD Summer school, for students and early researchers, as an annual event at international level - Define integration in the Arena, the alliance digital infrastructure - Set guidelines for integrating open practices training into institutional 	<p>and microcertificate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue the Open Practices International Workshop, as a yearly event at international level, with open access published papers - Continue the development of local, integrated by each partner, workshops, webinars, open days for open practices - Further develop the Open Practices PhD Summer school, for students and early researchers - Establish and feed a digital knowledge hub with open resources and access to research libraries. 	<p>research summer school</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seek external collaboration to co-develop or integrate high-quality support and training materials. - Identify community needs: Continuously engage with both internal teams and external stakeholders to understand evolving needs for support and training. - Curate and adapt resources: Find, evaluate, and adapt existing open training resources and toolkits, making them easily accessible to the community. - Organize dynamic learning events - Champion best practices to encourage a culture of openness, experimentation, 	<p>practices on open practices& citizen science.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advocate for the recognition of open practices in professional development. - Initiate user community grow 	<p>knowledge hub with ≥ 50 OERs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Secure budget line for training. 	

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	development programs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage faculty members. - Further develop, in depth training on data sharing, open-access publishing, open innovation, open education and citizen science. - Identify and select best example platforms (e.g. data collection in citizen science projects) and showcase these tools to the broader ecosystem. 	and community-driven science.			
4. Integrate Open Practices into incentives and assessment in E³UDRES²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set strategic goals and principles for how open practices and citizen science should be rewarded and recognized across the alliance. - Define reward structures for researchers and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a recognizing, awarding system for innovators and ambassadors in Open Practices at the level of the Alliance - Coordinate the development of shared guidelines, criteria, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test different incentive models (e.g., open-access publication grants, awards for open innovation, badges, career benefits). - Gather feedback from faculty, researchers, and students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement and adapt these incentives at the local level, gathering feedback from users and helping to refine the system in practice. - Advocate for systemic change in academic recognition of open practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alliance joins EOSC Draft “Open Practice Recognition Framework” + award scheme. Pilot calls in Alliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognition framework approved First 3 “Open Practice” awards issued

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	educators adopting open practices. - Align open practices with institutional performance metrics and funding models.	processes for assessing and incentivizing OP and CS. - Facilitate discussions with HR and funding agencies on integrating open practices into career progression. - Develop assessment frameworks that recognize open science contributions.	- Seek external best practices for integration.	- Publish case studies demonstrating the impact of open-practices incentives. - Engage policymakers to integrate open science into national research assessments.		
5. Integrate the digital tools and platforms of the E³UDRES² Arena within the R&I ecosystem for open practices and citizen science (for research and education)	- Integrate this vision into E³UDRES² Arena , the digital infrastructure for research, with the features dedicated to open practices and citizen science. - Secure funding and partnerships for platform	- Coordinate E³UDRES² Arena development by connect ICT teams, researchers, and educators to co-create or to implement digital tools. (open source) - Ensure interoperability of platforms for research,	- Scout innovative digital tools, pilot new technologies, and initiate collaborations with external tech providers or communities. (open source) - Pilot digital repositories, open-access databases, and citizen science platforms.	- Promote adoption of digital tools across E³UDRES² and beyond. - Publish user guides, tutorials, and best practices. - Engage the broader academic and industry community in open-source development. (Feedback loops)	Integrate areas for Open education and Open Science in E³UDRES² Arena Integrate Zenodo and other OS tools Build prototype dashboard fed by ORCID, Crossref, APIs.	100 researchers /projects/ papers published with OA

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	continuous development.	education, and innovation with other alliances.	- Test usability and adoption across different institutions.			
6. Establish mechanism and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Open Science and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define strategic goals and key dimensions (KPI) for measuring the impact of open practices and citizen science. - Align KPI frameworks with European Commission requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop collaborative mechanisms for tracking progress (dashboards, reports, etc.). - Involve all stakeholders in KPI validation and refinement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test data collection methods for tracking open science adoption. - Explore innovative metrics, pilot new evaluation methods, and collaborate externally to align with international standards. - Pilot self-assessment tools for institutions and researchers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate KPI results through open reports. - Share success stories to encourage wider adoption. - Advocate for KPI-based policy changes at the national and EU level. - Feedback loops to refine and improve the measurement system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-design 15 core indicators Build prototype dashboard fed by ORCID, Crossref, APIs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicator set ratified Dashbord online
7. Involvement of external stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define engagement strategies for businesses, policymakers, and civil society. - Set strategic priorities for which external stakeholders to engage and why (e.g., industry, NGOs, local communities). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate stakeholder mapping, engagement strategies, and partnership models across the alliance. - Act as the primary hub for stakeholder interactions. - Organize co-creation sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively reach out, build new connections, co-create activities with external partners, and bring fresh perspectives into projects. - Develop joint research projects with external partners. (E.g. Policy Labs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement stakeholder engagement locally, maintain relationships, and integrate external input into research and education activities. - Publicize stakeholder involvement through media and outreach campaigns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Host 2 "Open-Innovation events Identify partnerships with stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Innovation events 50 external partners attracted

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	First Phase implementation	KPIs
	- Establish partnerships with non-academic organizations.	with industry, government, and communities.	- Facilitate knowledge transfer between academia and society.	- Create policy briefs advocating for stronger academia-industry-government collaboration.		
8. Integration of Citizen Science in the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the strategic role of Citizen Science within E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem. - Establish guidelines models for CS projects. - Showcase best practice examples for additional funding for citizen science projects to enlarge engagement and impact (networking, media attention, engagement angels and liminal locations) - Ensure citizen science aligns with institutional research strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate collaborations between researchers and citizen scientists. - Develop shared frameworks, guidelines and support structures for integrating citizen science projects across institutions. (Workshops and training) - Develop ethics and data-sharing guidelines for citizen engagement. (workshops and training) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot citizen science initiatives in various disciplines. - Connect with external citizen science networks, and promote best practices. - Test engagement models and impact measurement tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate Citizen Science activities and amplify the impact across regions and institutions. - Promote citizen science success stories. - Organize public events to increase participation. - Advocate for stronger policy support for citizen-driven research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish CS guidelines Run training sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CS guidelines public and integrated Citizens involvement and contributions: 100

- See Annex 2: Roles&responsibilities for each action of the Implementation Plan for Node OP&CS.
- See Annex 3: Comprehensive KPI Monitoring for Node OP&CS Implementation Plan

6 References

- Brown, J. S., & Duguid, P. (2000). *The social life of information*. Harvard Business School Press.
- Dron, J., & Anderson, T. (2014). *Teaching crowds: Learning and social media*. Athabasca University Press. <https://www.aupress.ca/books/120235-teaching-crowds/>
- Duguid, P. (2005). The art of knowing: Social and tacit dimensions of knowledge and the limits of the community of practice. *The Information Society*, 21(2), 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972240590925311>
- Lesser, E. L., & Storck, J. (2013). Networks of Practice. In M. A. Runco (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Creativity* (2nd ed., pp. 169–173). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-7163-9_371-1
- Siemens, G. (2005). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 2(1), 3–10. https://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan_05/article01.htm
- Wasko, M. M., & Faraj, S. (2005). Why should I share? Examining social capital and knowledge contribution in electronic networks of practice. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(1), 35–57. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148667>
- Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of practice: Learning, meaning, and identity*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511803932>
- Wenger, E., McDermott, R., & Snyder, W. (2002). *Cultivating communities of practice: A guide to managing knowledge*. Harvard Business School Press.
- European University Association – Digital transformation map for Higher education, (2024), <https://eua-dtm.eu/>
- Andone, D., & Brown, M. (2022). *Strategy and organisational culture* (17; p. 21). European University Association. https://eua.eu/downloads/publications/eua%20tpg%20report_%20strategy%20and%20organisational%20culture.pdf
- Andone, D. (2022, June 22). *Digital Education Strategy at Politehnica University of Timisoara*. EDEN Annual Conference 2022, keynote presentation, Timisoara. <https://elearning.upt.ro/en/educatie-digitala/>
- Andone, D., Mihaescu, V., Vert, S., Ternauciuc, A., & Vasii, R. (2020). Students as OERs (Open Educational Resources) co-creators. *2020 IEEE 20th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT)*, 34–38. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICALT49669.2020.00017>
- [1] D4.1 Report on identified practices - identifies opportunities for collaboration and policy development to address challenges and capitalize on open science initiatives barriers needs, (2023), Report of E³UDRES² ENT-R-E-NOVATORS
- [2] D4.2. ENTRENOVATORS SWOT training in OS_OI_OE_OA, (2024), Report of E³UDRES² ENT-R-E-NOVATORS

ANNEX I | Open practices Strategies and Implementation plans at the level of each university in the Consortium

A.I.1 – Governance and Mission in the Node Open practices for each partner university

IPS' vision is based on the guidelines and recommendations of the European Commission, UNESCO and the Portuguese Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education, and with the principles of Open Science. IPS's mission focuses on the advancement of science and the wide dissemination of knowledge for the benefit of society, adopting Open Science practices that are reproducible and responsible, and is aligned with the guiding principles of the Code of Ethics and Conduct of the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (<http://hdl.handle.net/10400.26/53637>), as well as the Intellectual Property Regulations of the IPS. <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/regulamento/436-2021-163441259>

IPS governance structure for open scientific and educational practices is based on strategic planning and commitment with its Open Science Policy

https://bibliotecas.ips.pt/files/Politica%20Ci%C3%Aancia%20Aberta_IPS.pdf and is supervised by the Institution's leadership, the Office for Innovation, Research and Development and The Department of Libraries and Documentation.

IPS's core policies for open scientific and educational practices are in line with international guidelines and recommendations (e.g., UNESCO, European Commission, and the Portuguese Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education) which were the basis for the elaboration of its Open Science Policy. The implementation of the Open Science Policy is planned over four years, evaluated and eventually revised every two years. It came into effect on February 13, 2023. It applies to all IPS staff, students, teachers, researchers, and partners.

IPS requires (point 4 of its Open Science Policy) that all publications resulting from the scientific and academic activity of its staff be deposited in its digital scientific repository.

IPS aligns its open scientific and educational practices with its Code of Ethics and Conduct of the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal. <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.26/53637>

At **UCLL** by 2028, degree programmes and expertise centres, through their projects and actions, bring about a demonstrable sustainable transformation in the thinking and behaviour of the involved stakeholders. Societal challenges form the basis for structured collaboration between programmes and expertise centres on concrete projects and actions. By 2026, strategic partnerships around selected core themes are recognisably established inside and outside the organisation. New strategic partnerships are jointly developed or existing ones are strengthened from within degree programmes and expertise centres. A joint

network of stakeholders, programmes and expertise centres is set up to define and implement collaborative projects and actions, with citizen and external stakeholder involvement.

<https://intranet.ucll.be/nl/medewerker/over-ucll/ucll-overkoepelend/missie-visie-en-strategie/wij-zijn-bruggenbouwers>

ViA, Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences facilitates the consolidation of an enterprising, inclusive, smart and technologically advanced future knowledge society at regional, national and international level.

This mission states that VUAS creates and advances evidence-based knowledge for the holistic development of people and the cultivation of talents throughout life. It is equally important that VUAS, in interaction with stakeholders, researches and addresses issues relevant to the growth of the society in an international and regional context. In addition, VUAS co-creates innovations for the sustainability of regions and societies. And finally, VUAS provides a sustainable and attractive, people-oriented environment for cooperation, work and growth for all stakeholders, striving to become an attractive employer in academia. (Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences Development Strategy 2023–2028, Strategic part).

Adherence to academic and research ethics ViA staff honestly treats the study and research process and the persons involved thereof. The staff respects the copyrights, intellectual property, work results of others, guarantees truthfulness of data used in research and the analysis carried out in academic and scientific research. In order to promote adherence to academic and research ethics at Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences, the following principles should be observed: honesty, openness, objectivity, unambiguity, respect for the rights of research participants, independence from sponsors, and acknowledgement of contribution of all persons involved in research.

The **St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (St. Pölten UAS)** recognises the profound importance Open Access and commits to the “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities“. Open Access refers to the free and public digital access to scientific findings. The idea is for users to be able to read, copy, disseminate, and print full texts without limitations, to search them, refer to them, and use them in any other legally conceivable manner without encountering any financial, legal, or technical barriers. Open Access publications are subject to a high degree of public accessibility and availability. Evidence shows that these sources are more frequently read and quoted than publications with limited access.

In addition, the St. Pölten UAS recognises the fundamental importance of open research data for guaranteeing and maintaining scientific integrity and high research quality. Easy and unconditional access to research data, taking into account the protection of personality rights and privacy, is a fundamental component of numerous research activities and constitutes a necessity for reviewing and validating research processes and outputs. Research data thus have a sustainable value for science and society. This Policy supports researchers in the processing, storage, alteration, use, dissemination, and erasure of research data, thereby reducing the risks associated with these activities. The St. Pölten University of Applied Science attaches great importance to compliance with the FAIR Principles for research data: findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

At STPUAS, Open Access is the publishing standard. In this context, the following guidelines apply:

For research outputs, the St. Pölten UAS recommends the first publication (also: Gold Open Access) under a free licence (preferably CC BY). Among other things, publishing activities are supported by framework contracts and publishing funds if no third-party funds are available. The St. Pölten UAS calls on its employees to actively use their secondary publishing rights (also: Green Open Access) and publish all of their research exclusively in repositories, such as established academic repositories or Phaidra, the St. Pölten UAS' institutional long-term repository, simultaneously to or after the expiry of the applicable embargo periods provided that no other legal or contractual obstacles prevent them from doing so.

The **Politehnica University of Timisoara UPT** main strategies since 2010 centres on: digitalization of education and research, use and promotion of Open Educational Practices (OER and OEP), development of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Open Access to scientific publications and Open Science services. In 2010, the UPT Strategic Plan introduced open access to knowledge and early OER initiatives. The 2021–2024 UPT Strategic Plan advanced open education, digital certificates, and open publishing. That same year, the Institutional Evaluation Report reinforced digitalization through Open Education, Open Science, and integrated OER. In 2022, the UPT Digital Strategy emphasised incorporating ICT tools, OER, and MOOCs, culminating in the UniCampus development as Romanian MOOCs. The 2022 Operational Plan proposed a dedicated Open Science service to support researchers. Finally, the 2024–2029 UPT General Strategy promotes open-access editorial production and enhanced online services. Overall, these policies reflect a longstanding commitment to openly sharing educational content, encouraging open research practices, and fostering digital transformation across teaching, learning, and publishing. Additionally, the Digital Education (eLearning Center previously), Politehnica Publishing House and the UPT Library have been key enablers for implementing open practices models, at large in the university.

UPT's governance framework for open initiatives relies on long-term strategic planning and oversight from university leadership. Across multiple documents (Strategic Plans 2010, 2021–2024, 2024–2029), the Senate and Administrative Council coordinate the inclusion of open educational resources, open science services, and digital technologies in institutional development. They ensure alignment with international guidelines (e.g., UNESCO) and facilitate collaboration among faculties, centers (CEL), and Library, promoting shared decision-making. This approach supports continuous improvement and resource allocation, all governed by Digital Education Department, the Research Office, UPT Library, UPT Publishing House.

A.I.2 – Policies

The university's core policies encourage integrating open access principles into all academic and research activities. Through official documents—Digital Strategies, Operational Plans, and Institutional Reports—UPT mandates open publishing of research outputs and supports MOOCs, OER, and open science platforms. Moreover, the strategic plans highlight digital and open education practices, emphasizing licensing that permits free reuse and adaptation. Clear policy statements also guide the adoption of new technologies and services, ensuring consistency in open innovation efforts.

UPT's ethical framework for open initiatives stresses responsible authorship, fair use of resources, and protection of intellectual property. UPT respects copyright while granting the Creative Commons rights to access and adapt educational materials in Unicampus.ro. Ethical transparency is also fostered through open science services offered by the UPT Library. The Ethics Council at the level of the Senate UPT.

Widening access lies at the heart of UPT's digital and open strategies. Through UniCampus and OER platforms, courses become globally accessible, removing traditional entry barriers. The UPT Library's open-access initiatives offer students and researchers free, immediate availability of publications. Additionally, specialized services (e.g., workshops, seminars, exhibitions, virtual tours) strengthen engagement for diverse communities.

By promoting open education, open science, and open publishing, UPT ensures broader participation and knowledge exchange, fostering innovation and lifelong learning opportunities for all.

UPT plays a significant role in national and international efforts to promote open science. By participating in projects and conferences, the university contributes to the development of policies and infrastructures that support open access to scientific knowledge. This involvement underscores UPT's dedication to fostering a transparent and collaborative research environment.

UPT actively engages in citizen science projects, encouraging public involvement in scientific research. Workshops and projects are organized to raise awareness and implement citizen science as part of the broader open science movement, highlighting key initiatives and frameworks. These initiatives demonstrate UPT's commitment to fostering open practices, enhancing accessibility, collaboration, and innovation in academia.

UPT is actively and consistently involved with events such as European Researcher's Night, Night of open museums, Romanian Science Festival, Flight Festival (Art & Tech Section). During 2023 when Timisoara was one of the European Capitals of Culture, the UPT campus hosted the most events all over Timisoara, with well awarded and recognized examples like Spotlight Heritage Timisoara and UPT Creative Campus.

The vision of the **Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)** in the field of open science is closely linked to the MATE 2030 strategic program. The university aims to widely disseminate the principles and practices of open science, thereby contributing to the transparency and collaboration of the scientific community. The MATE 2030 ¹ program focuses on several key areas related to open science, including educating the future generation of agricultural leaders, generating innovative knowledge in the Carpathian Basin, and strengthening knowledge-intensive agriculture to enhance national competitiveness. At MATE, the goals and activities related to open initiatives were outlined in the Institutional Development Plan for the period 2021–2024, and later in the current MATE 2030 strategic document. The implementation of the objectives set out in the strategic document is overseen by the Rector, while specific areas are coordinated by the Vice-Rector for Education and for Science and Quality Assurance, as well as the Heads of Institutes. Compliance with national and international guidelines is continuously monitored, with particular attention to research projects that are directly funded by the European Union Policies.

¹ MATE: Webinars for PhD students [Call for webinar]. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/webinar-2025> [2025-04-16]

The university's regulations related to Open Science are included in the Publication and Publishing Policy of the MATE². This policy covers areas such as the operation of the university's institutional repositories, the management of open access copyright (Creative Commons) for works published by the university, and the mandatory use of DOI identifiers to enhance the visibility and traceability of publications.

At MATE, ethical issues related to open science are governed by the university's Code of Ethics and the Intellectual Property Management Regulations. It is important to note that the copyright licenses applied by MATE are detailed in the university's Publication and Publishing Regulations. The university provides several open science services, operated by the University Library (e.g., institutional repositories, OJS journals), which further strengthen the ethical transparency of the university's scientific activities.

The Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life Sciences, as a member institution of the Hungarian Electronic Information Service National Programme, subscribes to the most important international scientific databases. According to the Open Access agreements, authors with a MATE affiliation may publish OA articles in publishers' journals at no additional cost. Based on the Publication and Publishing Policy of the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, the institution aims to incorporate Open Access into the Open Science strategy, which not only ensures the freedom and transparency of research but also contributes to the development of the scientific community. Implementing Open Access requires a long-term commitment and continuous efforts to ensure that researchers can easily access and use scientific results. A successful Open Access strategy is based on an appropriate legal framework, infrastructure, research support, ongoing communication, and effective monitoring and evaluation of research.

The university also operates its own Open Access/DIAMOND journals (<https://journal.uni-mate.hu/>)³ and has established and maintains a central open access repository (<https://press.mater.uni-mate.hu/>)⁴, which enables researchers to share their work and publications with the wider community. Some of the university's research data are stored in an EPrints repository; however, the use of international cloud-based research data repositories (e.g., Zenodo) is much more common. In Hungary, there are currently efforts underway to establish a national-level central management system for research data across the entire academic network. As a result, MATE has not yet made a final decision on whether it will archive its research data in an institutional data repository or within a centralized national service in the long term.

By signing the Berlin Declaration, MATE committed itself to supporting open access publications and encouraging free access to researchers' work. By endorsing the Statement on Open Science (<https://nkfih.gov.hu/hivatalrol/hivatal-hirei/ujabb-egyetem-nyilt-tudomany>)⁵, the University further aims to

² MATE: Webinars for PhD students [Call for webinar]. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/webinar-2025> [2025-04-16]

³ MATE: MATE Egyetemi Innovációs Hét. [Call for webinar]. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://www.uni-mate.hu/esem%C3%A9ny/-/content-viewer/ei7/20123> [2025-04-16]

⁴ MATE: Let's be Open!: Nyílt tudomány: lehetőségek és kihívások. [Call for webinar]. In: Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/beopen2024> [2025-04-16]

⁵ MATE: Open Acces publikálás. [The open access publishing possibilities of MATE]. In: Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage. URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/open-acces> [2025-04-16]

promote transparency in scientific processes and ensure the accessibility of research results to both the professional community and the broader public.

MATE actively participates in citizen science projects, encouraging public involvement in scientific research, for example in the Ivy Mapping Project (<https://entkonyvtar.wordpress.com/ivy-mapping-project/>)⁶. Workshops (<https://lib.uni-mate.hu/en/hir/-/content-viewer/one-size-does-not-fit-all-workshop-on-citizen-science/1118028>)⁷ and projects are organized to promote and implement citizen science, highlighting key initiatives and frameworks as part of the broader open science movement. These initiatives demonstrate MATE's commitment to fostering open practices, enhancing accessibility, collaboration, and innovation in academia.

A.I.3 – Training, Support and Infrastructures

At IPS, training is provided by the librarians through 1-2 h workshops and seminars, generally online. An example are the seminars and webinars held during the International Open Access Week, which usually takes place in the last week of October.

International Workshop on Open Science and Open Education, held on Friday, 7th of June, 2024.

Open Science training to Professors and Researcher held twice a year (provided by librarians).

At ViA, training is provided by the librarians, senior researchers through 1-2 h workshops and seminars, generally online. An example are the seminars and webinars held during the International Open Access Week, which usually takes place in the last week of October.

Seminars for PhD students about Open Science issues. Researchers' afternoon and Doctorands breakfast are monthly activities. Some seminar and workshop topics: "Introduction about Statistical data portal "Kā orientēties datos?", "How to find and use open statistical data", "Open science tools", "Researcher's impact - Metrics and Quartiles".

ViA Library offers personal advice on Open Access, Open Science issues <https://va.lv/biblioteka/pakalpojumi> Annual European Researcher's Night as a platform to share experience and get knowledge about various science issues. <https://va.lv/en/component/content/article/eiropas-zinatnieku-nakts-vidzemes-augstskolas-iespeja-aizrautigi-piedzivot-zinatnieka-ikdienu>

Annual event Vidzeme Innovation week organised by Vidzeme Planning Region also as a platform to raise awareness, for example in 2024 was a seminar "Open science and innovation interactions."

<https://innovation.vidzeme.lv/lv/arhivs/2024/pasakumi/2024-03-01/seminars-atvertas-zinatnes-un-inovaciju-mijiedarbiba.html>

Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences doctoral students get acquainted with the new doctoral model and discuss the concept of open science.

⁶ MATE: MATER Press – University Publications repository. URL: <https://press.mater.uni-mate.hu/> [2025-04-16]

⁷ MATE: MATE Journals – Journals of the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences. URL: <https://journal.uni-mate.hu/> [2025-04-16]

At STPUAS, starting with WS2025, an accredited training program “OER Practitioner” is offered by the Service and Competence Center for Teaching/Learning Development and Educational Offers (LEARN). This training focuses on the handling of Open Educational Resources.

Source: https://www.fhstp.ac.at/en/audiences/lecturers/open-educational-resources/open-educational-resources?set_language=en

On the topic of Open Access, our library offers an FAQ page and personal advice. Currently, the St. Pölten UAS provides its staff members with the necessary infrastructure (e.g., Phaidra), which is continuously further developed, for electronic publishing and archiving. The St. Pölten UAS provides its staff members with organisational support in publishing in Open Access journals and supports the financing of incurred publication costs from the UAS' internal publishing funds. The St. Pölten UAS offers guidance to all staff members in scientific publishing in Open Access journals and offers them support in legal issues. <https://www.fhstp.ac.at/en/campus/library/open-access>

At MATE, the University Library plays the key role in organizing training sessions and workshops related to open initiatives. It regularly provides training on this topic for PhD students (<https://lib.uni-mate.hu/webinar-2025>)⁸ and is also a frequent contributor to the University Innovation Week program series (<https://www.uni-mate.hu/esem%C3%A9ny/-/content-viewer/ei7/20123>)⁹, or in October 2024, as part of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project, the event Let's be Open! – Open Science: Opportunities and Challenges was organized, focusing on the main themes of Open Access, Open Data, and Citizen Science (<https://lib.uni-mate.hu/beopen2024>)¹⁰.

The University Library supports Open Access publishing by offering expert advice and facilitating the establishment of Read'n'Publish agreements (<https://lib.uni-mate.hu/open-acces>)¹¹.

The Library is also responsible for organizing and supporting the IT infrastructure related to MATE's open initiatives, such as operating institutional repositories (<https://press.mater.uni-mate.hu/>)¹² and providing Open Journal System services (<https://journal.uni-mate.hu/>)¹³.

⁸ MATE: Webinars for PhD students [Call for webinar]. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/webinar-2025> [2025-04-16]

⁹ MATE: MATE Egyetemi Innovációs Hét. [Call for webinar]. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://www.uni-mate.hu/esem%C3%A9ny/-/content-viewer/ei7/20123> [2025-04-16]

¹⁰ MATE: Let's be Open!: Nyílt tudomány: lehetőségek és kihívások. [Call for webinar]. In: Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/beopen2024> [2025-04-16]

¹¹ MATE: Open Acces publikálás. [The open access publishing possibilities of MATE]. In: Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage. URL: <https://lib.uni-mate.hu/open-acces> [2025-04-16]

¹² MATE: MATER Press – University Publications repository. URL: <https://press.mater.uni-mate.hu/> [2025-04-16]

¹³ MATE: MATE Journals – Journals of the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences. URL: <https://journal.uni-mate.hu/> [2025-04-16]

UPT has hosted multiple events focusing on open education and science. For instance, the 12th edition of the International Workshop during Open Education Week 2025 addressed challenges in open science and education, emphasizing responses to emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and blockchain, featuring presentations from international experts and discussions on integrating open practices into university activities.

The International Open Education Week Workshops since 2013.

<https://elearning.upt.ro/en/?s=open+education+week&trp-form-language=en>

The e-learning department (DeL) organises the Open Education Week Workshop since 2013 (10 editions in 2023). This is an international workshop organized by the Polytechnic University of Timișoara, through the ID/IFR and e-Learning Center with the support of the EDEN Europe and IEEE Romania associations, during the Open Education Week of each year, supported by Open Education Global.

DeL also organizes the Digital Skills and Competences workshop for 9 years. In 2024, the workshop hosted more than 300 participants in a hybrid format with the title Workshop digital skills in artificial intelligence and community - DigiSkills 2024, which was followed right after by the workshop Empowering Innovation through Open Science and Citizen Science.

A.I.4 – Collaboration and partnerships

At IPS collaboration and partnership occurs mainly at training level, with other Portuguese universities. One example is the conduction of a webinar by the University of Minho for the IPS community during the International Open Access Week. Through its librarians, IPS is also a member of national working groups related to Open Science training, Data stewards, etc. that share and promote the good practices used in each institution.

One of VIA collaboration and partnership occurs at training level, with the National Open Access desk. Everyone can attend webinars, conferences and other activities, for example during the International Open Access Week. <https://www.napd.lu.lv/atverta-piekluve/atverta-piekluve/aktivitates-1/>

ViA has joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

<https://va.lv/en/jaunumi-category-blog-2/vidzeme-university-of-applied-sciences-joins-international-research-and-assessment-coalition>

STPUAS is member of FNMA, a national network for e-learning, and took part in the working group “AG Open Educational Resources”, which resulted in the creation of a brochure about Open Educational Resources: <https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/detail/o:2106327>

The St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (St. Pölten UAS) recognises the profound importance Open Access and commits to the “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities”.

One of MATE's earliest collaborations in the field of Open Science is its membership in the HUNOR (<https://www.napd.lu.lv/atverta-piekluve/atverta-piekluve/aktivitates-1//>)¹⁴. HUNOR is a consortium established by Hungarian universities with the primary goal of supporting the practical implementation of open initiatives within the Hungarian scientific community. HUNOR also created and maintains the website.

As part of advancing open initiative goals, MATE signed a cooperation agreement with the Hungarian Intellectual Property Office to promote intellectual property education, enabling students and faculty to manage and utilize their intellectual assets more consciously.

E³UDRES² (Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions) is a European university alliance that brings together institutions like MATE to foster innovation, open science, and sustainable regional development. It promotes collaboration between students, researchers, and local communities to solve real-world challenges through interdisciplinary and entrepreneurial approaches.

UPT has a very strong stakeholder ecosystem which also involves activities on OE, OI and OS. UPT has an Executive Committee with members from the industry and public authorities, thus ensuring strong involvement in the needs of the community and the local industry ecosystem. Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Education practices are encouraged also through this entity.

UPT has been a member of EDEN (European Distance and E-learning Network) for 30 years, organizing several events each year promoting Open Education and Open Science. Also, through individual members nominated in leadership position of the association, UPT has been actively involved in tailoring European strategies and policies regarding Open Education.

UPT is a full member in COARA and signed the Berlin Declaration for Open Access.

A.I.5 – Monitoring and evaluation

Currently at IPS, there is no standard monitoring and evaluation mechanism for the Open Science strategy implementation. However, for purposes related to the career progression of researchers and professors, open access publication is taken into account, either through open access journals or through deposit in the IPS digital scientific repository.

VIA - The implementation of the strategies of academic and scientific departments and their link to the performance indicators set in the VUAS Strategy is monitored annually, with the Rector of VUAS and the deans of faculties and directors of institutes agreeing upon the results to be achieved within the year.

UPT - Integrates monitoring and evaluation of Open Education (OE) within its institutional quality assurance processes, academic career advancement evaluations, and external reviews conducted by ARACIS at both

¹⁴ DEENK: HUNOR (HUNGARIAN Open Repositories). In: Open Science webpage. URL: <https://openscience.hu/hunor/> [2025-04-16]

institutional and degree levels. OE activities are particularly monitored through incentives linked to Open Access (OA) publishing, focusing on indexed scientific outputs.

Best practices include:

- Annual evaluation of OA publications at both individual and departmental levels, which contributes to decisions on career promotion and merit-based bonuses.
- UPT Library's systematic assessment of OA publications, ensuring their visibility and impact are recognized within institutional performance metrics.

At MATE, there is currently no centralized mechanism at the university level for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of the Open Science strategy. However, several aspects are already regulated at sub-institutional levels. For instance, certain internal research funding schemes require compliance with specific Open Science principles which are subject to monitoring and evaluation during the funding period (for example Flagship Research Groups Programme) ¹⁵. In addition, individual incentive programmes are in place that set expectations aligned with the goals of the Open Science strategy (e.g. participation in Open Science training), and the fulfilment of these requirements is monitored (for example: Research Excellence Programme) ¹⁶.

A.I.6 – Funding and incentives

At IPS, only Open Access publishing is subject to funding and incentive mechanisms.

Career progress evaluation of professors is benefited by the number of Open Access publications they have. Also, IPS is part of the Transformative Agreement (coalition-s.org), an European consortium that allows publishing free of charge in a list of open access journals. Finally, there is an internal channeled fund that IPS researchers can apply for. For instance, for the year 2025, each researcher can receive support up to €3,000 for scientific journals that are indexed and classified in the 1st or 2nd quartile in their respective scientific fields (including proofreading), as well as those listed in the ABS List, and up to €750 for publications in indexed conference proceedings, particularly in Scopus or Web of Science.

ViA there is no separate funding for OS activities. Each year, institutes and faculties receive development grant, which can also be spent on APC costs, research activities etc.

ViA researchers have financial benefits for reviewing and/or publishing in Q1, Q2 journals.

St. Pölten UAS provides two separate Open Access funds to help St.-Pölten-UAS-affiliated authors cover Article Processing Charges (APCs) for Open Access publications in academic journals:

FWF Open-Access Block Grant (Third Party) and St. Pölten UAS Publication Fund.

¹⁵ MATE: Research Excellence Programme. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage (2025-03-05) URL: <https://research.uni-mate.hu/hu/about-the-programme-rep> [2025-04-16]

¹⁶ MATE: Flagship Research Groups Programme. In Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences webpage (2025-03-05) URL: <https://research.uni-mate.hu/hu/about-the-programme> [2025-04-16]

The STPUAS Publication Funding awarded to a publication is limited to a maximum of EUR 2,200.–. The amount awarded depends on the applicable Article Processing Charges. Source: <https://www.fhstp.ac.at/en/campus/library/open-access>

MATE highly values and actively promotes the publication of research in Open Access (OA) journals. This includes collaboration with OA publishers and ensuring that the university maintains subscriptions to appropriate OA platforms. To support this effort, read and publish agreements are established as part of the Hungarian Electronic Information Service National Programme (<https://eisz.mtak.hu/index.php/en/open-access-english/open-access-agreements.html>)¹⁷

To encourage Open Access publishing among researchers, MATE has implemented an incentive system. Specifically, researchers who publish their work in Q1 or Q2 ranked journals receive an annual bonus in recognition of their contributions.

UPT has several incentive systems rewarding researchers who published in well established journals. UPT through the national research system has incentives for publishing open access, without paying an article publication charge (APC), supported from national funds. The same cooperates and share OER and open education within different institutions.

UPT also has a number of journals with open access policies which are supported financially by the university:

- <http://www.jauh.upt.ro/index.php/JAUH/open-access>, <https://sc.upt.ro/ro/mastercom>
- Journal of Electrical Engineering, <http://jee.ro/index.php/jee/ino>
- Journal of Architecture, Urbanism and Heritage, <http://www.jauh.upt.ro/index.php/JAUH/about>, <http://www.jauh.upt.ro/index.php/JAUH/open-access>
- Acta Technica Corviniensis, <https://acta.fih.upt.ro/>
- Mastercom, <https://pgsj.upt.ro/about/about-the-journal>
- Nonconventional Technologies Review, <http://www.revtn.ro/index.php/revtn/about>
- EU level Funding for OE/OA/OS/OI

A.I.7 – EU Funding and incentives

We mapped of some current EU funding strands that explicitly support open science, open education, and open innovation. Each entry gives the official programme (or specific call), a 1-sentence “why it matters,” typical beneficiaries, the budget/grant scale where available, and where to look for live or upcoming calls on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal or the programme’s own site. This list is only indicative and not exhaustive.

¹⁷ EISZ: Open Access agreements. In: Electronic Information Service National Programme (EIS) webpage. URL: <https://eisz.mtak.hu/index.php/en/open-access-english/open-access-agreements.html> [2025-04-16]

Table EU Funding and Incentives.

Programme / Call	What it funds & who can apply	Scale & key dates	Where to look
Open Science			
Horizon Europe – central R&I framework	All research actions must practise open science (open access, data management plans, citizen science etc.). Separate open science policy & WIDERA calls fund training, skills, citizen science pilots, repositories.	€95.5 bn overall (2021-27). 2025 WIDERA calls open 2 Dec 2024; first stage deadline 10 Apr 2025.	EU Funding & Tenders Portal
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) – e-infrastructure	Builds the shared cloud & data space for EU researchers; includes cascade grant schemes for tools and services.	2025 OSCARS 2nd open call: lump sum grants €100k–€250k; deadline 14 May 2025.	EOSC Association “Calls & Grants” page
Open Research Europe (ORE) – publishing platform	Horizon beneficiaries publish peer reviewed articles & underlying data free of charge, with open peer review.	Always open; publication costs covered by the Commission.	ORE platform
Open Education			
Erasmus+ 2025 Call (Key Action 2 etc.)	Cooperation partnerships that create open educational resources , open licence courses, digital pedagogy, teacher training, micro credentials.	Budget ~€5 bn for 2025; most KA2 deadlines Feb–Apr 2025.	Erasmus+ “Funding calls” page
European Universities Initiative (within Erasmus+)	Alliances of HEIs developing joint campuses, open course catalogues, shared virtual mobility.	Up to €14 m per alliance over four years; next call expected Sept 2025.	Erasmus+ Portal (same as above)

Programme / Call	What it funds & who can apply	Scale & key dates	Where to look
EIT HEI Initiative – Call 4 (2025 27)	Grants for consortia of universities + industry to embed entrepreneurship & open innovation in curricula; includes creation of openly licensed training material.	Up to €1.34 m per project (25 months); Phase 1 starts 1 Apr 2025.	EIT HEI Initiative site
Open Innovation			
EIC Accelerator (Horizon Europe Pillar III)	Equity + grant support for deep tech SMEs/startups bringing breakthrough innovations to market.	Grants up to €2.5 m + equity up to €15 m; “EIC Accelerator Open” cut offs three times a year (next June 2025).	EIC Accelerator page
EIC Pathfinder Open	Consortia research on radically new technologies (“exploratory open innovation”).	Grants up to €3 m; 2025 deadline 7 Mar 2025.	EIC Pathfinder page
EIT Knowledge & Innovation Communities (KICs)	Large public private hubs (e.g., EIT Digital, Culture & Creativity) that run open calls for pilots, accelerators, living labs.	New KIC call (Water/Marine) opened 2025; typical projects €250k–€3 m.	EIT “Call for KIC proposals”
Digital Europe Programme (DEP)	Deployment focused funding for data spaces, AI testing facilities, European Digital Innovation Hubs that keep outputs open & reusable.	2025–27 WP budgets €3.2 bn; first 2025 calls open 15 Apr 2025 , deadline 2 Sep 2025.	Digital Europe programme page

For Open access and open publishing the funding and incentives information can be found on EU support for open access:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/open-access_en

OpenAire information: <https://www.openaire.eu/a-quick-guide-to-open-access>

Programme / funder	How it works	Who's eligible & typical ceiling	Where to check / apply
Open Access			
Horizon Europe (all pillars)	APCs or book processing charges are <i>eligible direct costs</i> provided the venue is fully OA (hybrid venues are not reimbursed). Costs must be in your proposal budget or added via an amendment.	Any Horizon Europe beneficiary; no fixed cap, but must follow your grant's overall budget rules.	HE Open Science guidance page (European Research Executive Agency)
European Research Council (ERC)	Same rule as above—OA fees are eligible if the outlet is 100 % OA; grantees must deposit papers within 6 m.	All ERC main schemes; within the grant's budget.	ERC Work Programme 2025 §2.2 (European Commission)
Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA)	Fellows and consortia may charge APCs/book fees to their MSCA budget; ORE platform also available free of charge.	DN, PF, COFUND, Staff Ex; within action budget.	MSCA Open Science brief (horizoneuropencpportal.eu)
COST Actions	Each Action's networking budget can be used to make articles/books OA; COST recommends Diamond/Gold routes and has an OA monitoring system.	Participants in an active COST Action; 100 % of fee.	COST OA strategy page (COST)
Open Research Europe (ORE)	Rapid publication, open peer review, indexing & long term archiving— no APCs ever (EU pays).	Any Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe beneficiary plus collaborators.	Always open; new article types and monograph pilot announced for Q4 2025. https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/
ZENODO	Based on OpenAIRE project, CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013. Zenodo code is itself open source.	Any researcher can publish and create community	https://zenodo.org/

Programme / funder	How it works	Who's eligible & typical ceiling	Where to check / apply
HORIZON-WIDERA-2025-ERA-01-22 "Support to cOAlition S & Plan S"	Operating grant to keep Plan S services (Journal Checker, Rights Retention, OAPEN upgrade) running and expand to OA books.	€0.2 m, single beneficiary (European Science Foundation); grant runs 2025 27.	HE WIDERA WP 2025 p.165
European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)	Joint OPERAS / Science Europe initiative that will launch cascade grants for Diamond journals & platforms (technical upgrades, governance, multilingual tooling).	First micro grant scheme expected Q3 2025, €10–50 k per journal.	OPERAS news 15 Jan 2025 (operas.hypotheses.org)
OpenAIRE "Funding for APC free OA journals & platforms"	Up to €200 k per bid to make Diamond/overlay journals interoperable (PID, metadata, peer review workflows).	12 winners, call opened Apr 2025, closes 30 Jun 2025.	OpenAIRE call brief (OpenAire)

ANNEX II | Roles & responsibilities for each action of the Implementation Plan for Node OP&CS

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
1. Establish the Open Practices Committee as a Network of Practitioners (Node) for Open Practices and Citizen Science at E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the strategic purpose and structure of the node. - Appoint 1 member from each partner university Appoint key representatives from different sectors (education, research, industry, and government). - Align node objectives with EU policies and institutional priorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Act as the coordinating hub for open practices and citizen science knowledge creation - Organize meetings, workshops, and decision-making sessions. - Facilitate knowledge exchange between stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drive external collaboration by engaging stakeholders to expand the network - Pilot node activities through small working groups. - Develop preliminary recommendations for implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate and disseminate node progress to internal and external stakeholders. - Publish reports, guidelines, and policy recommendations. - Promote the node's role in cross-sector collaborations. - Amplify the impact of the network by scaling participation and fostering societal transformation. 	Lack of engagement from diverse sectors; unclear roles.	Clear governance structure, onboarding sessions, and incentives for participation.
2. Develop E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem Policies on OE/OA/OS/OI/CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set the policy framework and ensure alignment with European standards (e.g., FAIR data, Open 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate discussions on best practices in policy development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-design and develop prototype policy guidelines with external stakeholders and test their feasibility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate finalized policies through open-access publications within each university Library 	Institutional resistance to adopting new open practices.	Highlight alignment with EU standards and showcase early success stories.

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	<p>EU education adoption, open practices.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define compliance guidelines for open access, research transparency, and citizen science. - Establish an open data steward and an open data management plan for the alliance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage university administrators, legal teams, and researchers in policy co-creation. - Ensure policies are adaptable for various institutional contexts. - engage the innovators and ambassadors for OE/OA/OS/OI/CS from each university. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct case studies on institutions successfully implementing OE/OA/OS/OI. - Pilot policy impact assessments. 	<p>and open access publications.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize policy advocacy events with external stakeholders. And integrate these in the workshops and webinars already established. - Collaborate with policymakers to scale policies beyond E³UDRES². 		
3. Develop/ Integrate support and training for open practices and citizen science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate the MOOC course Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS, as the main training practices - Continue the Open Practices International Workshop, as a yearly event at international level, with open access published papers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate the MOOC course Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS as an interdisciplinary training programs for researchers, educators, policymakers, industry partners, and citizens. Validate the modules as microcredentials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ignite innovation: experiment with and promote new methods for open science and citizen science training. - Motivate to develop new modules and content for OE/OA/OS/OI/CS and integrate them at the Alliance level - Motivate participation to the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Scale up successful programs across institutions: the Foundations of OE/OA/OS/OI/CS, the Open Practices PhD Summer school, workshops, webinars. - Organize webinars and public engagement initiatives to 	Low participation in training programs.	Embed training into institutional development; offer certificates and micro-credentials.

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue the development of local, integrated by each partner, workshops, webinars, open days for open practices - Allocate funding and resources for training initiatives. - Further develop the Open Practices PhD Summer school, for students and early researchers, as an annual event at international level - Define .integration in the Arena, the alliance digital infrastructure - Set guidelines for integrating open practices training into institutional 	<p>and microcertificate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continue the Open Practices International Workshop, as a yearly event at international level, with open access published papers - Continue the development of local, integrated by each partner, workshops, webinars, open days for open practices - Further develop the Open Practices PhD Summer school, for students and early researchers - Establish and feed a digital knowledge hub with open resources and access to research libraries. 	<p>research summer school</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seek external collaboration to co-develop or integrate high-quality support and training materials. - Identify community needs: Continuously engage with both internal teams and external stakeholders to understand evolving needs for support and training. - Curate and adapt resources: Find, evaluate, and adapt existing open training resources and toolkits, making them easily accessible to the community. - Organize dynamic learning events - Champion best practices to encourage a culture of openness, experimentation, 	<p>promote best practices on open practices& citizen science.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advocate for the recognition of open practices in professional development. - Initiate user community grow 		

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	development programs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage faculty members. - Further develop, in depth training on data sharing, open-access publishing, open innovation, open education and citizen science. - Identify and select best example platforms (e.g. data collection in citizen science projects) and showcase these tools to the broader ecosystem. 	and community-driven science.			
4. Integrate Open Practices into incentives and assessment in E³UDRES²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set strategic goals and principles for how open practices and citizen science should be rewarded and recognized across the alliance. - Define reward structures for researchers and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a recognizing, awarding system for innovators and ambassadors in Open Practices at the level of the Alliance - Coordinate the development of shared guidelines, criteria, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test different incentive models (e.g., open-access publication grants, awards for open innovation, badges, career benefits). - Gather feedback from faculty, researchers, and students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement and adapt these incentives at the local level, gathering feedback from users and helping to refine the system in practice. - Advocate for systemic change in academic recognition of open practices. 	Lack of recognition for open practices in evaluations.	Engage HR and funders early; align with international trends in research assessment.

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	<p>educators adopting open practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Align open practices with institutional performance metrics and funding models. 	<p>processes for assessing and incentivizing OP and CS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate discussions with HR and funding agencies on integrating open practices into career progression. - Develop assessment frameworks that recognize open science contributions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seek external best practices for integration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publish case studies demonstrating the impact of open-practices incentives. - Engage policymakers to integrate open science into national research assessments. 		
<p>5. Integrate the digital tools and platforms of the E³UDRES² Arena within the R&I ecosystem for open practices and citizen science (for research and education)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate this vision into E³UDRES² Arena, the digital infrastructure for research, with the features dedicated to open practices and citizen science. - Secure funding and partnerships for platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate E³UDRES² Arena development by connect ICT teams, researchers, and educators to co-create or to implement digital tools. (open source) - Ensure interoperability of platforms for research, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scout innovative digital tools, pilot new technologies, and initiate collaborations with external tech providers or communities. (open source) - Pilot digital repositories, open-access databases, and citizen science platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote adoption of digital tools across E³UDRES² and beyond. - Publish user guides, tutorials, and best practices. - Engage the broader academic and industry community in open-source development. (Feedback loops) 	<p>Arena low adoption.</p>	<p>Involve end-users in development, provide ongoing support.</p>

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	continuous development.	education, and innovation with other alliances.	- Test usability and adoption across different institutions.			
6. Establish mechanism and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Open Science and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define strategic goals and key dimensions (KPI) for measuring the impact of open practices and citizen science. - Align KPI frameworks with European Commission requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop collaborative mechanisms for tracking progress (dashboards, reports, etc.). - Involve all stakeholders in KPI validation and refinement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Test data collection methods for tracking open science adoption. - Explore innovative metrics, pilot new evaluation methods, and collaborate externally to align with international standards. - Pilot self-assessment tools for institutions and researchers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate KPI results through open reports. - Share success stories to encourage wider adoption. - Advocate for KPI-based policy changes at the national and EU level. - Feedback loops to refine and improve the measurement system. 	Difficulty in measuring impact or inconsistent data.	Develop user-friendly tools, align with existing EU frameworks, ensure stakeholder buy-in.
7. Involvement of external stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define engagement strategies for businesses, policymakers, and civil society. - Set strategic priorities for which external stakeholders to engage and why (e.g., industry, NGOs, local communities). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate stakeholder mapping, engagement strategies, and partnership models across the alliance. - Act as the primary hub for stakeholder interactions. - Organize co-creation sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively reach out, build new connections, co-create activities with external partners, and bring fresh perspectives into projects. - Develop joint research projects with external partners. (E.g. Policy Labs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement stakeholder engagement locally, maintain relationships, and integrate external input into research and education activities. - Publicize stakeholder involvement through media and outreach campaigns. 	Limited commitment from external partners.	Demonstrate value, co-create benefits, ensure shared goals.

Action Point	Pillars	Nexus	Sparks	Waves	Risks	Mitigation
	- Establish partnerships with non-academic organizations.	with industry, government, and communities.	- Facilitate knowledge transfer between academia and society.	- Create policy briefs advocating for stronger academia-industry-government collaboration.		
8. Integration of Citizen Science in the E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define the strategic role of Citizen Science within E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem. - Establish guidelines models for CS projects. - Showcase best practice examples for additional funding for citizen science projects to enlarge engagement and impact (networking, media attention, engagement angels and liminal locations) - Ensure citizen science aligns with institutional research strategies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitate collaborations between researchers and citizen scientists. - Develop shared frameworks, guidelines and support structures for integrating citizen science projects across institutions. (Workshops and training) - Develop ethics and data-sharing guidelines for citizen engagement. (workshops and training) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot citizen science initiatives in various disciplines. - Connect with external citizen science networks, and promote best practices. - Test engagement models and impact measurement tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate Citizen Science activities and amplify the impact across regions and institutions. - Promote citizen science success stories. - Organize public events to increase participation. - Advocate for stronger policy support for citizen-driven research. 	Low citizen participation or unclear impact.	Design engaging projects, communicate impact clearly, provide training for researchers and citizens.

ANNEX III | Comprehensive KPI Monitoring for Node Open Practices & Citizen Science Implementation Plan

1. Establish the Open Practices Committee as a Network of Practitioners (Node) for Open Practices and Citizen Science at E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem						
Role	Tasks per role	KPI	Risks	Mitigation	Status	Notes
Pillars	Define the strategic purpose and structure of the node.	Percentage of ecosystem members who understand and approve the strategic objectives (measured via a survey).	Lack of alignment between ecosystem members, unclear objectives.	Hold early workshops for alignment and regular check-ins to clarify objectives.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshop to kick start the new strategic ecosystem model.
	Appoint key representatives from different sectors (education, research, industry, and government).	Number of representatives from different sectors (at least 3 sectors represented).	Resistance to appoint representatives or lack of engagement from sectors.	Clearly define the role and benefits of participation, incentivize sector involvement.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Align nodes' objectives with EU policies and institutional priorities.	Ecosystem policy documents aligned with EU guidelines (e.g., FAIR data, OER adoption).	Misalignment with EU policies or local institutional priorities.	Work closely with EU policy advisors to ensure alignment and consult internal stakeholders.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Iterative process (never finished)
Nexus	Act as the coordinating hub for open practices and citizen science knowledge creation	Number of open practices discussions held per quarter.	Low participation or engagement in discussions.	Promote the importance of the discussions via communication campaigns and make meetings engaging and accessible.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Organize meetings, workshops, and decision-making sessions.	Number of organized sessions (meetings, workshops, etc.) and participants.	Poor attendance or low-quality interactions during meetings.	Choose optimal times for meetings, offer remote participation options, and ensure topics are highly relevant.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Facilitate knowledge exchange between stakeholders.	Percentage of stakeholders satisfied with knowledge exchange (can be measured via a feedback survey).	Knowledge exchange may not be effective or impactful.	Use follow-up surveys to identify areas of improvement and adjust the knowledge exchange formats accordingly.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

Sparks	Drive external collaboration by engaging stakeholders to expand the network	At least 3 key representatives of different sectors involved in the external sounding board.	No engagement of external stakeholders	Clearly define the role and benefits of participation, incentivize sector involvement.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Pilot node activities through small working groups.	1 successful pilot project conducted	Pilot projects fail or do not provide useful insights.	Develop a solid framework for pilot projects, monitor closely, and adjust quickly if issues arise.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Develop preliminary recommendations for implementation.	Pilot implemented or not	Recommendations are not actionable or not adopted by stakeholders.	Ensure that recommendations are feasible, well-researched, and aligned with the interests of stakeholders.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Waves	Communicate and disseminate node progress to internal and external stakeholders.	Number of external stakeholders reached via communication tools (newsletters, publications, meetings).	External stakeholders do not engage or respond to communications.	Ensure communications are clear, targeted, and tailored to the audience. Use multiple communication channels.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Publish reports, guidelines, and policy recommendations.	Number of published reports and guidelines per year (with emphasis on open access).	Reports or guidelines may not be widely read or adopted.	Use an open-access platform for distribution, and actively promote the publications.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Promote the node's role in cross-sector collaborations.	Number of new collaborations initiated with external stakeholders (businesses, governments, other universities).	Low interest or commitment from cross-sector partners.	Actively reach out to potential partners, offer clear mutual benefits, and foster long-term relationships.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Amplify the impact of the network by scaling participation and fostering societal transformation.	Quantitative and qualitative data (measuring impact by progress of participation, community engagement, innovation and transformation)	Low engagement or participation	Address risks related to societal transformation by promoting inclusivity and ensuring that the benefits of the transformation are equitably distributed across different communities.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

2. Develop E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem Policies on OE/OA/OS/OI/CS						
A2	Pillars	Set the policy framework and ensure alignment with European standards (e.g., FAIR data, OER adoption).	Number of policy frameworks aligned with EU standards (e.g., FAIR data, OER adoption).	Misalignment with EU policies or conflicting institutional goals.	Regular consultations with EU policy advisors and ensure buy-in from all institutional levels.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.
		Define compliance guidelines for open access, research transparency, and citizen science.	Number of compliance guidelines defined and published.	Guidelines may not cover all necessary areas, causing implementation gaps.	Engage with legal experts and stakeholders from the start to ensure comprehensive and inclusive guidelines.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.
Nexus	Facilitate discussions on best practices in policy development.	Number of discussions/ workshops held on policy best practices. (Identify and select best practices)	Low participation or lack of engagement from all institutions or stakeholders.	Promote the importance of the discussions through targeted communications and ensure clear agendas.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP4 of the Ent-r-e-novators project: SWOT, vision mission and implementation plan.
	Engage university administrators, legal teams, and researchers in policy co-creation.	Percentage of key stakeholders (administrators, legal teams, researchers) actively involved in co-creation.	Resistance from university administrators, legal teams, or researchers to engage in co-creation.	Showcase the value and relevance of co-creation in policy design, and involve all stakeholders early in the process.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Ensure policies are adaptable for various institutional contexts. Two-track strategy at the consortium and institutional level.	Number of adaptable policy frameworks developed.	Policies may be too rigid, leading to challenges in adoption across different institutions.	Regularly gather feedback during the policy development phase and be flexible in adjusting the guidelines.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP4 of the Ent-r-e-novators project: SWOT, vision mission and implementation plan. With overarching eco-system model.
Sparks	Co-design and develop prototype policy guidelines with external stakeholders and test their feasibility.	Number of external stakeholders involved in co-creation.	Prototype policies may not address practical implementation challenges.	Facilitate structured workshops or collaborative meetings with external stakeholders.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Implementation plan WP4.

	Conduct case studies on institutions successfully implementing OE/OA/OS/OI.	Number of case studies conducted on successful policy implementations.	Case studies may not provide sufficient or representative data.	Select a diverse range of institutions to pilot and analyze the outcomes systematically.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Case studies identified within consortium (WP4).
	Pilot policy impact assessments.	Number of pilot tests conducted with external stakeholders and feedback gathered on the feasibility of the guidelines.	Difficulty in measuring policy impact or lack of actionable data.	Develop clear, measurable criteria for impact assessments and involve external evaluators to ensure objectivity.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Waves	Disseminate finalized policies through open-access publications.	Number of finalized policies published and disseminated through open-access platforms.	Lack of uptake or awareness of the policies.	Promote policies through multiple channels (webinars, newsletters, collaborations with stakeholders).	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Organize policy advocacy events with external stakeholders.	Number of advocacy events organized and attended by external stakeholders.	Poor attendance or limited external stakeholder engagement.	Engage stakeholders early, tailor the event content to their interests, and incentivize attendance through benefits.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Collaborate with policymakers to scale policies beyond E³UDRES².	Number of policy collaborations initiated with national or EU policymakers.	Policymakers may not be willing to adopt or scale the policies.	Develop strong partnerships with policymakers, demonstrate the value of the policies, and align with EU priorities.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
A3	3. Develop/Integrate support and training for open practices and citizen science					
Pillars	Allocate funding and resources for training initiatives.	Amount of funding/resources allocated (e.g., budget per year).	Insufficient funding or resources allocated.	Conduct thorough needs assessments to justify resource allocation and ensure proper budgeting early on.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Define digital infrastructure requirements.	Number of infrastructure needs defined and addressed.	Incomplete or inadequate digital infrastructure.	Conduct a comprehensive audit of current infrastructure and identify gaps early in the planning phase.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	

	Ensure alignment with strategy.	Alignment of training programs with institutional and EU strategies (measured via a strategic alignment review).	Misalignment with institutional goals or EU policies.	Regularly consult with institutional leaders and EU representatives to ensure alignment of the training programs.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Set guidelines for integrating open practices training into institutional development programs.	Number of institutions that integrate open practices into their development programs (measured via feedback surveys).	Lack of integration into institutional development programs.	Provide clear guidelines, examples of integration, and incentivize participation by showcasing best practices.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
Nexus	Design interdisciplinary training programs for researchers, educators, policymakers, industry partners, and citizens.	Number of interdisciplinary programs developed.	Low participation or engagement from industry partners, researchers, or educators.	Engage stakeholders early in the process, demonstrate the value of interdisciplinary approaches, and incentivize participation.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Establish and feed a digital knowledge hub.	Number of training materials uploaded and accessed.	Low engagement with the digital knowledge hub.	Promote the hub through institutional channels and make the platform user-friendly, accessible, and well-advertised.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Develop train-the-trainer programs. (Pilot hands-on workshops on data sharing, open-access publishing, open innovation, open education and citizen science.)	Number of workshops, MOOCs, trainings, OER, ...	Low engagement in workshops, ...	Engage stakeholders early in the process, demonstrate the value of open practices and citizen science, and incentivize participation.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Open practices and citizen science workshops held in all institutions during the entire duration of the Ent-r-e-novators project.
	Identify and select best example platforms (e.g. data collection in citizen science projects) and showcase these tools to the broader ecosystem. Facilitate usability workshops	Number and diversity of platforms to facilitate open practices and citizen science. Number of usability workshops. Adoption rate and satisfaction rate. Impact on project outcomes.	Accessibility and usability lacks.	Platform performance feedback loops	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Zenodo (open access)

	Engage faculty members	Number of faculty engaged in training initiatives (measured via sign-ups/registrations).	Low engagement.	Provide clear benefits for each group (e.g., professional development, certifications, networking).	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Open practices and citizen science workshops held in all institutions during the entire duration of the Ent-r-e-novators project.
Sparks	Ignite innovation: experiment with and promote new methods for open science and citizen science training.	Number of new methods.	No direct new insights	Encourage cross-disciplinary collaboration, harness emerging technologies, & feedback loops to refine existing methods.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Seek external collaboration to co-develop or integrate high-quality support and training materials.	Number of external stakeholders.	Low engagement	Provide clear benefits for each group (e.g., professional development, certifications, networking).	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Identify community needs: Continuously engage with both internal teams and external stakeholders to understand evolving needs for support and training.	Frequency of needs assessment conducted	Lack of participation from key stakeholders	Use surveys, one-on-one interviews, and interactive platforms to gather broad feedback and ensure active involvement.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	Engagement strategies (WP5).
	Curate and adapt resources: Find, evaluate, and adapt existing open training resources and toolkits, making them easily accessible to the community.	Number of resources adapted and made accessible	Insufficient quality or relevance of existing resources	Regularly update resources, involve experts in content evaluation, and ensure resources are tailored to the needs of the community.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science.
	Organize dynamic learning events	Number of events held and participant feedback	Low participation or insufficient engagement	Use targeted invitations, create interactive sessions, and ensure the events are highly relevant and engaging.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science.

	Champion best practices to encourage a culture of openness, experimentation, and community-driven science.	Number of best practices adopted by stakeholders	Resistance to new methods or reluctance to change	Share success stories, provide incentives, and engage key influencers to model best practices within the community.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science
Waves	Scale up successful training programs across institutions.	Number of institutions adopting scaled-up training programs.	Lack of adoption across institutions.	Create clear case studies to demonstrate the effectiveness and value of the training programs.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 (MOOC's on OI/OE/OA/OS in development) and WP5 workshop and training on citizen science (developed and now in testing phase)
	Organize webinars and public engagement initiatives to promote best practices on open practices & citizen science.	Number of webinars and public events organized.	Low attendance or lack of interest in public engagement initiatives.	Use targeted communication, and provide interactive or engaging formats in webinars and events.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science
	Advocate for the recognition of open practices in professional development.	Number of institutions or bodies that formally recognize open practices in professional development (e.g., certifications).	Open practices not being recognized or integrated into professional development frameworks.	Advocate through professional organizations, offer certifications, and promote the value of open practices.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science
	Initiate user community growth.	Number of active users in community forums or groups.	Low engagement in the user community.	Foster an online community with regular events, discussions, and shared resources.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Workshops of WP4 and WP5 on open practices and citizen science. Dissemination in European networks (e.g. ECSA)

A4 4. Integrate Open Practices into incentives and assessment in E³UDRES²						
Pillars	Set strategic goals and principles for how open practices and citizen science should be rewarded and recognized across the alliance.	Percentage of researchers and educators adopting open practices.	Resistance to changes in reward structures.	Involve stakeholders early in the design process and align with existing goals.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Define reward structures for researchers and educators adopting open practices.	Evaluate effectiveness of award structures.	No effectiveness.	Involve stakeholders early in the design process and align with existing goals.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Align open practices with institutional performance metrics and funding models.	Percentage of institutional performance metrics and funding models integrating open practices.	Institutional resistance to updating metrics.	Conduct workshops with HR and funding departments to align goals.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
Nexus	Coordinate the development of shared guidelines, criteria, and processes for assessing and incentivizing OP and CS.	2-3 pilots to test within the institutions.	No effectiveness.	Involve stakeholders early in the design process and align with existing goals.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	
	Facilitate discussions with HR and funding agencies on integrating open practices into career progression.	Number of discussions and agreements made with HR and funding agencies.	Lack of alignment or interest from HR or funding bodies.	Present research demonstrating benefits for career development.	Under Review – The action is under internal evaluation or feedback.	
	Develop assessment frameworks that recognize open science contributions.	Number of open science contributions recognized in assessments.	Difficulty defining measurable open science contributions.	Engage experts to validate and define measurable contributions.	Under Review – The action is under internal evaluation or feedback.	
Sparks	Test different incentive models (e.g., open-access publication grants, awards for open innovation, badges, career benefits).	Number of applicants and recipients of grants and awards.	Low participation or lack of impactful results.	Create compelling calls for participation and offer tangible rewards.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

	Gather feedback from faculty, researchers, and students.	Percentage of faculty, researchers, and students satisfied with the incentive models.	Low response rate to feedback mechanisms.	Make feedback easy, anonymous, and incentivize participation.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Seek external best practices for integration.	Guide on best practices.	No internal translation	Involve stakeholders early in the design process and align with existing goals.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Waves	Implement and adapt these incentives at the local level, gathering feedback from users and helping to refine the system in practice.	Number of publications, talks, or outreach initiatives on open practices.	Limited external interest or slow uptake of change.	Collaborate with thought leaders and policymakers for advocacy.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Advocate for systemic change in academic recognition of open practices.	Number of academic institutions that adopt or revise recognition policies to include open practices.	Resistance from university administrators, legal teams, or researchers to engage.	Engage with university leaders early in the process, emphasize the long-term benefits of recognizing open practices, and provide examples of successful implementations.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Publish case studies demonstrating the impact of open-practices incentives.	Number of case studies published and disseminated.	Case studies may not show sufficient impact.	Select successful institutions and ensure robust data.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Engage policymakers to integrate open science into national research assessments.	Number of policy discussions or papers on open science integration.	Slow policy change or lack of interest.	Build a coalition of stakeholders and present clear evidence.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
A5	5. Integrate the digital tools and platforms of the E³UDRES² Arena within the R&I ecosystem for open practices and citizen science (for research and education)					
Pillars	Define the vision and digital infrastructure requirements for open practices and citizen science.	Percentage of defined digital infrastructure requirements met.	Unclear infrastructure needs or technical gaps.	Consult with IT teams and stakeholders early to align requirements.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP3 and 4
	Secure funding and partnerships for platform development.	Amount of funding secured and partnerships established.	Difficulty securing funding or finding suitable partners.	Prepare a compelling case and emphasize tool benefits.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	

Nexus	Coordinate platform development or integration efforts, ensuring interoperability and alignment across the ecosystem.	Number of platforms developed or integrated across the ecosystem that meet interoperability standards. User percentage.	Platforms may not meet the required interoperability standards, leading to siloed systems.	Actions to minimize or address those risks, such as clear guidelines, user training, and ongoing feedback loops.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Connect ICT teams, researchers, and educators to co-create or to implement digital tools. (open source)	Number of collaborative workshops and meetings held.	Lack of engagement or communication.	Foster regular communication and ensure shared understanding of roles.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Ensure interoperability of platforms for research, education, and innovation.	Number of successful integrations with existing platforms.	Technical incompatibility or lack of integration.	Ensure compatibility through regular testing and expert collaboration.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Sparks	Scout innovative digital tools, pilot new technologies, and initiate collaborations with external tech providers or communities. (open source)	Number of pilot projects successfully implemented. Number of external stakeholders	Low adoption or poor user experience.	Engage early adopters, collect feedback, and improve iteratively.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Pilot digital repositories, open-access databases, and citizen science platforms.	Number of pilot projects successfully implemented.	Low adoption or poor user experience.	Engage early adopters, collect feedback, and improve iteratively.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Test usability and adoption across different institutions.	Percentage of users satisfied with usability and adoption.	Poor usability or low engagement.	Conduct thorough usability testing and improve based on feedback.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Waves	Promote adoption of digital tools across E³UDRES² and beyond.	Number of institutions and stakeholders adopting the tools.	Low adoption or lack of interest.	Highlight success stories, provide support, and offer incentives.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Publish user guides, tutorials, and best practices.	Number of guides, tutorials, and best practices published.	Lack of comprehensive resources.	Create accessible and updated resources for all users.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	See Open Practices inspiration Guide (developed in WP 4)

	Engage the broader academic and industry community in open-source development.	Number of contributors to the open-source project.	Low participation in open-source development.	Actively engage with contributors, offer recognition, and provide support.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
A6	6. Establish Mechanism and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Open Practices and citizen science					
Pillars	Define strategic goals and key dimensions (KPI) for measuring the impact of open practices and citizen science.	Number of KPIs defined and aligned with open science goals.	Lack of clear or relevant KPIs.	Involve stakeholders early and align KPIs with EU-level objectives.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Preliminary research, SWOT and other work done in WP4 will form the starting point.
	Align KPI frameworks with European Commission requirements.	Percentage of KPIs aligned with European Commission requirements.	Misalignment with European Commission policies.	Work closely with EU advisors to ensure alignment.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
Nexus	Develop collaborative mechanisms for tracking progress (dashboards, reports, etc.).	Number of collaborative mechanisms developed and operational.	Low adoption or inconsistent data reporting.	Ensure user-friendly interfaces and provide training.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Involve all stakeholders in KPI validation and refinement.	Percentage of stakeholders involved in KPI validation.	Lack of engagement or differing views.	Facilitate regular consultations and feedback loops.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Sparks	Test data collection methods for tracking open science adoption.	Number of tested data collection methods implemented.	Inconsistent or inaccurate data collection methods.	Pilot test methods, gather feedback, and refine.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Explore innovative metrics, pilot new evaluation methods, and collaborate externally to align with international standards.	Level of external collaboration, impact on outcomes, feedback from stakeholders	Lack of buy-in of external stakeholders	Involve key external partners and stakeholders from the beginning to ensure buy-in and alignment with their needs and expectations.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Pilot self-assessment tools for institutions and researchers.	Number of self-assessments completed.	Low participation or inaccurate self-reporting.	Incentivize participation and provide support.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

Waves	Disseminate KPI results through open reports.	Number of open KPI reports published.	Reports not widely read or used.	Promote reports through multiple channels.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Share success stories to encourage wider adoption.	Number of success stories shared.	Difficulty finding success stories.	Actively seek successful cases and offer documentation support.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Advocate for KPI-based policy changes at the national and EU level.	Number of policy changes influenced by KPI data.	Limited policy impact or resistance from policymakers.	Engage policymakers early and collaborate with advocacy groups.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Feedback loops to refine and improve the measurement system.	Feedback from stakeholders	Limited or low-quality feedback.	Actively encourage stakeholders to provide feedback through regular check-ins, structured surveys, or workshops to ensure that diverse viewpoints are considered.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
A7	7. Involvement of External Stakeholders					
Pillars	Define engagement strategies for businesses, policymakers, and civil society.	Number of engagement strategies developed and approved.	Lack of engagement or misalignment with interests.	Tailor strategies to each group and highlight mutual benefits.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Set strategic priorities for which external stakeholders to engage and why (e.g., industry, NGOs, local communities).	Percentage of stakeholder engagements aligned with strategic priorities. (Quality assessment, review cycle)	Difficulty engaging prioritized stakeholders (e.g., lack of interest or availability). Internal disagreement on which stakeholders to prioritize	Develop tailored value propositions for each stakeholder group, highlighting specific mutual benefits (e.g., visibility, innovation partnerships, societal impact). Use transparent decision-making processes	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Establish partnerships with non-academic organizations.	Number of partnerships with non-academic organizations.	Difficulty in securing partnerships or low interest.	Provide clear value propositions and emphasize mutual benefits.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

Nexus	Act as the primary hub for stakeholder interactions.	Number of interactions and communications with external stakeholders.	Overburdening communication channels or lack of coordination.	Set up a dedicated communication team and clear channels for regular updates.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Coordinate stakeholder mapping, engagement strategies, and partnership models across the alliance.	Number of external stakeholders successfully engaged. Satisfaction rate (survey). Number of partnership models co-created.	Inconsistent stakeholder mapping across institutions, leading to gaps or overlaps. Partnership models are not attractive or sustainable for stakeholders.	Develop a shared stakeholder mapping template and provide training or guidance to ensure consistency across the alliance. Co-design partnership models with stakeholder input to ensure they meet mutual needs and provide tangible benefits.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Organize co-creation sessions with industry, government, and communities.	Number of co-creation sessions and participation rates.	Low attendance or unproductive sessions.	Select relevant topics, invite key stakeholders, and offer incentives.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Sparks	Develop joint research projects with external partners (e.g., Policy Labs).	Number of joint research projects initiated and completed.	Delays in project initiation or misalignment with partners.	Set clear expectations and develop detailed project plans.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Actively reach out, build new connections, co-create activities with external partners, and bring fresh perspectives into projects.	Number of new external partners engaged and number of co-created activities launched.	Low response rate or limited interest from external partners.	Tailor outreach messaging to highlight mutual benefits, and leverage existing networks for warm introductions.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Facilitate knowledge transfer between academia and society.	Number of knowledge transfer activities (workshops, publications).	Difficulty in translating research into actionable outcomes.	Simplify findings and focus on practical applications.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Learnings from WP5
Waves	Publicize stakeholder involvement through media and outreach campaigns.	Number of media mentions, press releases, and outreach materials.	Limited media coverage or poor visibility.	Develop strong media relationships and create engaging content.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Implement stakeholder engagement locally, maintain relationships, and integrate external input into research and education activities.	Number of local stakeholders actively engaged and number of research/education activities influenced by external input.	Difficulty maintaining long-term engagement with stakeholders.	Set up regular touchpoints (e.g., meetings, newsletters), and actively involve stakeholders in decision-making processes.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	

	Create policy briefs advocating for stronger academia-industry-government collaboration.	Number of policy briefs created and distributed.	Policy briefs not reaching the right audience.	Target key policymakers and ensure briefs are evidence-based and action-oriented.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
A8	8. Integration of Citizen Science in the E³UDRES² R&I Ecosystem					
Pillars	Define the strategic role of Citizen Science within E³UDRES² R&I ecosystem.	Progress towards a documented strategic framework adopted by partners.	Delay in consensus-building across institutions.	Facilitate regular consultation meetings and iterative drafts to align stakeholders.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Establish guidelines for citizen science projects.	Number of projects supported and aligned with guidelines.	Insufficient funding or unclear guidelines.	Ensure robust and flexible funding models and communicate benefits clearly.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP5: D5.1.
	Showcase best practice examples for additional funding for citizen science projects to enlarge engagement and impact (networking, media attention, engagement angels and liminal locations)	Number of best practice examples showcased and amount of additional funding secured.	Low visibility or lack of interest from potential funders and partners.	Use targeted communication campaigns, organize showcase events, and involve successful project ambassadors to promote examples.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP5: D5.2.
	Ensure citizen science aligns with institutional research strategies.	Percentage of research strategies incorporating citizen science.	Institutional resistance to citizen science.	Engage institutional leaders and demonstrate value through pilot projects.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
Nexus	Facilitate collaborations between researchers and citizen scientists.	Number of active collaborations between researchers and citizen scientists.	Lack of collaboration.	Provide collaboration platforms and regular check-ins.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Develop shared frameworks, guidelines and support structures for integrating citizen science projects across institutions. (Workshops and training)	Number of institutions adopting the shared frameworks and number of workshops held.	Inconsistent adoption across institutions.	Tailor frameworks to institutional needs and provide continuous support via workshops and training.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	ILL, training and workshops done within WP5.

	Develop ethics and data-sharing guidelines for citizen engagement. Workshops and training.	Number of guidelines created and adopted.	Ethical concerns or data privacy issues.	Ensure clear guidelines and provide training for all participants.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
Sparks	Pilot citizen science initiatives in various disciplines.	Number of pilot projects conducted.	Low participation.	Offer incentives, promote widely, and create a user-friendly experience.	Not started - Action is planned but not started yet	
	Connect with external citizen science networks, and promote best practices.	Number of external networks engaged and best practices promoted.	Lack of engagement from external networks.	Build strong communication strategies and establish mutually beneficial partnerships.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	European Citizen Science Association is using the package to help citizen scientist and researchers in CS projects.
	Test engagement models and impact measurement tools.	Number of models tested and feedback collected.	Difficulty in measuring impact.	Develop clear methods for tracking and feedback.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	WP 5: Maturity Model with engagement competencies and incompetencies.
Waves	Promote citizen science success stories.	Number of success stories published.	Limited media coverage.	Use multiple platforms for promotion.	Completed – The action has been fully executed.	
	Disseminate Citizen Science activities and amplify the impact across regions and institutions.	Number of dissemination events, reach of activities across regions and institutions.	Limited reach or low engagement.	Utilize targeted communication channels, collaborate with local influencers, and ensure accessible, engaging content.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	
	Organize public events to increase participation.	Number of public events and participants.	Poor attendance or engagement.	Advertise well, use engaging content, and involve stakeholders.	In Progress – The action is actively being worked on.	Citizen Science workshop

	Advocate for stronger policy support for citizen-driven research.	Number of advocacy efforts and policy changes.	Policy resistance.	Use case studies, data, and engage policymakers with evidence-based arguments.	Planned – The action is planned but not yet started.	Citizen Science Policy Lab
--	---	--	--------------------	--	--	----------------------------

E³UDRES²
**ent.r.e.
novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

**POLITECNICO
SETUBAL**
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY

HUNGARIAN UNIVERSITY OF
AGRICULTURE AND LIFE SCIENCES

Universitatea
Politehnica
Timișoara

**UC Leuven
Limburg**
MOVING MINDS

VIDZEMES
AUGSTSKOLA

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency [REA]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.